

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

WP3 – HESS Dimensioning, Integration and Verification of Developed Software Tools

T3.1 – Modelling, managing and sizing HESS methodology for efficient grid integration of distributed HESS resources.

Submission date: 30th June 2024

Project Acronym	INTERSTORE
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01
Grant Agreement N°	101096511
Project Start Date	01-01-2023
Project End Date	31-12-2025
Duration	36 months

INFORMATION

Written By	Sara Golmaryami, Alexandre Lucas (INESC) Elyas Rakhshani, Jose Manuel Ruiz (HES)	2024-03-30 2024-06-06
Checked by	Alexandre Lucas (INESC)	2024-06-21
Reviewed by	Erdem Gümrükcü, Fabian Sommer (EAT), Nithin Manuel, Andres Acosta (RWTH)	2024-05-30
Approved by	Antonello Monti (RWTH Aachen University) – Project Coordinator	2024-06-25
Status	Final	

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

CO	Confidential	
CL	Classified	
PU	Public	X

VERSIONS

Date	Version	Author	Comment
30-11-23	0.1	Sara Golmaryami/Alexandre Lucas (InescTec)	Table of Contents - draft
28-03-24	0.2	Sara Golmaryami / Alexandre Lucas (InescTec)	Chapter 1 and 2 content
09-04-24	0.3	Elyas Rakhshani (HessTec)	Content of chapter 3 included
30-04-24	0.4	Alexandre Lucas (InescTec)	Conclusions and Introduction.
03-05-24 20-06-24	0.5 1	Alexandre Lucas (InescTec); Elyas Rakhshani (HessTec)	Editing

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

InterSTORE is an EU-funded project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101096511.

DISCLAIMER

The sole responsibility for the content of this report lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

While this publication has been prepared with care, the authors and their employers provide no warranty with regard to the content and shall not be liable for any direct, incidental or consequential damages that may result from the use of the information or the data contained therein.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ESS	Energy Storage System
BSS	Battery Storage System
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
DTW	Dynamic Time Warping
LP	Linear Programming
SoC	State of Charge
GFM	Grid Forming converter
UCAP	Ultracapacitor
POD	Power Oscillation Damping
PAJ	Phase Angle Jump
P	Active power
Q	Reactive power
SOE	State of Energy
VI	Virtual Inertia
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PLL	Phase Locked Loop
FLL	Frequency Locked Loop
AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
CAPEX	Capital expenditures
OPEX	Operating expenses
INMS	Intelligent Node Management System
VSC	Voltage Source Converter
PNIEC	National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan
RL	Reinforcement Learning
EMS	Energy Management System
LTS	Long-Term Strategy

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 Review of Hybridization and Control Approaches	10
1.2 Multi-Service Strategy in Hybridization Approaches.....	24
2 Hybrid Energy Storage System Sizing Model	27
2.1 Proposed Methodology	27
2.2 Recurring Pattern Identification	28
2.2.1 Generic Load Analysis – InterSTORE PT Pilot example.....	29
2.2.2 Dynamic Time Warping Algorithm.....	29
2.2.3 Clustering Algorithm	31
2.2.4 Load Profile Identification	32
2.3 Battery Optimization Scheduling	33
2.3.1 Optimization Model.....	34
2.3.2 Signal Dispatch Identification.....	38
2.4 Battery Hybridization Model.....	42
2.4.1 Cut-off Principles.....	42
2.4.2 Hybridization Curve.....	44
2.5 Commercial solution	47
2.6 Model Validation and Performance.....	49
2.7 Benefits of the Methodology for InterSTORE	51
2.7.1 Python Open-Source Implementation.....	51
3 Multiservice Approach for HESS System.....	52
3.1 The Challenges of High-RES Integration	52
3.2 Grid Services.....	56
3.3 Proposed Multiservice Methodology	60
3.4 Example of Multiservice Assessment in Different Scenarios: HESStec Approach	62
3.4.1 Test Scenario1: HESS with Wind Power	62
3.4.2 Test Scenario2: HESS with PV Power Plant.....	67
3.5 Benefits of the Multiservice Methodology for InterSTORE	68
4 Conclusions	70
5 REFERENCES	72
6 LIST OF TABLES.....	77
7 LIST OF FIGURES.....	78

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of this report is to present the developments achieved in InterSTORE, specifically in task 3.1, dedicated to the modelling, managing and sizing of hybrid energy storage systems (HESS) for efficient grid integration of distributed HESS resources. This report will hence present the methodology and tools to design, dimension and operate a HESS, providing the perspective from which HESS could be explored to outperform a single battery storage unit. The methodology foresees:

- a) Developing an adapted battery-like model for a HESS based on distributed storage resources combination, such as, stationary batteries of different technologies, EV Batteries, or home batteries. The model will provide sizing solutions independently of the technology. This will be done by identifying the existing demand profile of the foreseen load(s), providing optimal dispatches for the storage system and a hybrid battery sizing technique.
- b) Integrating the technology selection in the hybridization problem to match existing commercial solutions, and validate the sizing model.
- c) Developing a management and exploration strategy to enhance the HESS performance.

The definition and design of the proper business model is a key aspect to determine the appropriate resource hybridization and sizing. Determining the proper use of the system is crucial for the sizing activity. In the sizing model development, three steps were considered:

- i) Identification of recurring patterns
- ii) Optimal dispatch of a battery system
- iii) Determining a hybridization curve and optimal sizing region

In this report, the model is presented with an actual example with real data from the Portuguese pilot, using data from an office building, to which a HESS is connected to, for energy support provision. The model is then validated with a full optimization approach and its performance is analysed.

With respect to performance, running the total model takes 30.45 seconds to process a full year of data, perform the optimization of dispatch and output the hybridization area. Most of the processing time (24 seconds) is attributed to the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) block to cluster the data. When compared to a full optimization approach model considered from the literature, our development outperforms it for large data sets, as presented in the provided example, for which the full optimization model may take several hours, depending on the optimizer used. However, if only 24 h datasets or smaller are considered, the full optimization approach is faster (around 1 sec) compared to the proposed model in this study (6.45 seconds). Another metric used in our model is the quantitative H indicator, which provides an optimal area of solutions, allowing for an alignment with commercial solutions. In contrast, other studies tend to neglect this practical linkage.

The validation step was achieved by comparing the results to a full optimization approach used for Renewable Energy Communities asset sizing. The result for the total energy capacity sizing from the full optimization approach model was 523.28 kWh, considering a battery efficiency of 90%, which is aligned with the example of the proposed model in this study (500 kWh). When given an initial capacity of 110 kWh already installed, the model proposed a new

installation of 353.88 kWh when a C-Rate of 0.73 was provided. This value compares to the 367.00 kWh provided by our model, which is acceptable for validating the results, given the relative difference of 4%. It should be said, however, that the comparing reference model does not allow for a match with commercial solutions. This is because the full optimization model only provides a single optimal solution regarding of its existence in real life. This in fact is a highlight of the proposed model in this study, which makes a match with existing commercial solution. Moreover, the reference model does not achieve the hybrid combinations by adjusting the C-Rates, resulting in an energy-based and power-based battery combination, as they are inputs to the optimization of the full optimization approach model and not outputs, as they are in our approach.

A conclusion of the report on this matter is that the hybrid storage sizing model shows the superiority of the hybrid system in terms of versatility, size and adaptability to physical constraints, making it a more favourable option compared to traditional single-battery systems. This is particularly pertinent when there is a need for:

- i) Storage capacity increase,
- ii) The case where one cannot rely on a single battery,
- iii) The case in which a given technology cannot be deployed in the same location as an already existing battery, for space, security or other constraints,
- iv) Complementarity of characteristic and performances.

Regarding the management and exploration strategy to enhance the HESS performance, the report presents and discusses the impact of a hybrid solution employing a coordinated approach that integrates multi-service functionality within the system, focusing on two HESS multiservice scenarios involving the effects of wind profiles, and a PV power plant.

- According to the first multiservice test, the obtained results, indicate that using only Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) lead to over-degradation of the battery, due to its exposure to high-frequency wind variations. However, when considering a Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS), a smoothed power profile is achieved by utilizing Ultra-Capacitors (UCAP) with high-power technology, to cover the high-frequency variations in wind. Consequently, the power battery is shielded from these rapid power fluctuations, preserving its degradation. In the case studied, it is important to note that due to size limitations of the UCAP, a saturation of the State of Charge (SOC) is observed. A larger UCAP in the system would result in better responses, thereby mitigating SOC saturation issues.
- Regarding the second multiservice test, within the case of setpoint following mode operation, it has been observed that significant energy or capacity may be required in two situations:
 - Firstly, when the setpoint significantly deviates from the actual wind production, necessitating sufficient capacity from BESS/HESS to bridge the gap between the wind generation and the setpoint.
 - Secondly, when the setpoint changes, there is a heightened demand for capacity or energy to ensure a smooth ramp control.
 - It is considered that this service is activated upon demand from Transmission System Operators (TSO) or power plant operators due to reliability or operational requirements. Additionally, for the successful implementation of this service, accurate forecasting is essential to meet all setpoints.
 - According to the obtained results from the second multiservice test with PV plant and market factors, it has been observed that the optimization algorithm, situated in the Grid core control layer within the cloud, is highly effective in

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

maximizing the economic returns of the entire power plant (comprising PV + BESS), through participation in the day-ahead energy market. Additionally, the physical control layer, located in our EMS layer called InMS uGrid, efficiently utilizes all surplus solar resources, by prioritizing the cheapest hours, thereby achieving maximum economic performance, particularly during central daylight hours, around 12:00.

The sizing and hybridization approach will be published openly and/or made available during the project duration under the Github project repository and resulting deliverables made available to the general public in the project's website and Zenodo.

1 Introduction

The recent increased interest surrounding energy storage systems (ESS) can be attributed to the advancements in technology and their ability to provide multiple services to grid and off-grid contexts. Each storage technology comes with its own set of characteristics, such as power and energy densities, efficiency, self-discharge rate, and distinct investment costs. Moreover, in practice, ESS are often designed larger than necessary to manage fluctuating peak power needs and to minimize system strain. Based on this, hybrid technologies have made a new epoch for ESS. Selecting a hybrid energy storage system (HESS) may offer a more durable, practical, and cost-efficient approach for certain use cases. To this matter, the concept of the HESS is based on the understanding that diverse ESS technologies offer complementary features, especially when considering power and energy density, cost, life cycle and other criteria that a single ESS cannot fulfil on its own.

Furthermore, due to the variety of energy storage technologies, many hybrid combinations can be formed, which can be used in various types of applications. Expanding on this, HESS combine multiple ESS technologies, capitalizing on their individual strengths to enhance power output. In fact, this approach increases the advantages of each incorporated technology while diminishing their respective shortcomings. One crucial aspect of HESS applications is determining its right storage power and capacity. Few methods and studies exist to dimension hybrid systems, which tend to take on a theoretical approach for HESS sizing. To fill in this gap, within InterSTORE, Task 3.1 set out to accomplish this dimensioning of hybrid combinations, taking a technology agnostic approach.

To fulfil this goal the task started by defining the following set of requirements:

- i) The model is required to start and finish at the same SOE (in the defined optimization time window, e.g. 24h), which would minimize the idle power and capacity;
- ii) provide several optimal solutions (to match commercial existing solutions);
- iii) the HESS tool would be technology independent, based on two different sizes, technologies or other technical characteristics;
- iv) should output quantifiable optimization options (H factor);
- v) have as an input a load diagram based on historical consumption;
- vi) development in an opensource environment and to be published openly.

This technology-independent sizing methodology of HESS is presented in chapter 2, and the control strategies under different scenarios, highlighting the higher performance of hybrid systems and its contribution to support renewable energy penetration with multi service functionalities, are described in chapter 3.

Chapter 2 is divided into four blocks. It starts by utilizing the DTW clustering technique to identify a recurring pattern in a yearly consumption dataset of a building. Having identified a load diagram as the demand to be satisfied, the chapter presents the battery optimization scheduling step. This is done by determining an optimal dispatch for a full day of operation, that is used as input to the next phase. The third part of the model delineates the hybridization area for the optimal HESS sizing model, identifying possible base and peak battery combinations. Ultimately, and fourth step with this hybridization area, this study aims to identify viable commercial solutions and provide technology selection information based on the variables determined.

The control strategies of multi-service operation for a hybrid combination, is then presented in chapter 3, in which two scenarios of operation are studied. The scenarios foresee storage

to support wind generation under different operating conditions and a PV power plant operation also with the support of batteries considering different market factor. The analysis considers the energy-based and power-based contributions of hybrid combinations with multi-service functionality to provide renewable energy support. It highlights the use of Ultra-Capacitors and the impact of operation strategies in the degradation of the batteries.

To better frame the scope of the core of the report, the document starts with a brief review of battery technologies and control approaches, here part of chapter 1.

1.1 Review of Hybridization and Control Approaches

This section will discuss the importance of hybridization and control approaches. To achieve this, energy storage system (ESS) technologies, as identified in the literature, can be categorized into three main types according to the form of energy stored:

- Mechanical
- Electrical/magnetic
- Chemical

Each type exhibits diverse characteristics, making them suitable for various applications [1–3]. Figure 1 presents a classification of ESS technologies, high power, and high energy to categorise ESS technologies, providing an appropriate framework for technology classification. This is supported by information from the literature [1,2,4].

Figure 1. Technology classification according to discharge times.

Examining their classifications and critical features is essential to understanding various technologies comprehensively. These include typical discharge times, storage durations, specific requirements, and whether the technology is employed behind or in front of the meter. Table 1 shows details of these aspects based on data compiled from the literature [1–3].

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Table 1. Technology characteristics, based on [1-3].

Classification	Technol.	Power rating (MW)	Energy rating (MWh)	Inst. Capacity	Inst. Power	Discharge time	Storage period	Storage Requirements
Electrochemical	Lithium-ion (Li-ion)	0,0010-500	25	up to 100 MWh	Several MW Front of meter/ Behind meter	min-hr	Short-mid-term	Medium-high power
	Lead-acid (Pb-Acid)	< 40	18-	up to 10 MWh	Some MW Front of meter/ Behind meter	s-h / ≤4h	Short-mid-term	Medium-high power
	Sodium-Sulphur (NaS)	< 34	254	<100 MWh	<10 MW Front of meter	sec-10h	Long term	Medium-power
	Flow batteries (Vanadium)	10-100	0,040-40	<100 MWh	<10 MW Front of meter	sec-10h	Long term	Medium-high power
Kinetic	Flywheels (FES)	0,250	0,025-5	up to 0,25 MWh	<5 MW Front of meter	ms-hr	Second-short-term	High-power
Magnetic	Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES)	0,010-10	15-5×	1-10 kWh	100 kW-5 MW Front of meter	ms-8s / 1min	Short-term	Medium-high power
Electrical	Supercapacitors (SCES)	10	-0.005	1-5 kWh	100 kW-5 MW Front/behind of meter	ms-1h	Short-term	High-power

In the hybridisation concept, ESS technologies may also fall into two primary categories, high-power and high-energy technologies [1], based on power capability and response time [5]. Specific power is consistent for particular applications and most storage technologies. If the specific power of a storage technology does not match the application, the system will have to be oversized in power or energy. A HESS combines two storage technologies to achieve a specific power that aligns better with the application's needs [6]. So, to improve the system reliability, reduce battery power fluctuations, and optimise storage sizes [7], hybrid systems with a combination of two or more distinct ESS technologies brought a widely recognised solution to energy storage challenges [8,9]. In the study [10], the authors explore a power management strategy designed to optimize the operation of microgrids integrated with HESS, which consists of batteries and ultracapacitors. They developed a grid-adaptive power management strategy that dynamically adjusts the microgrid's behaviour and associated storage systems based on real-time conditions. The strategy aims to enhance the stability and efficiency of microgrids by intelligently managing the charge and discharge cycles of ESS, thus providing support to the grid during various operational conditions, such as excess or deficit power scenarios. In another study [11], the authors discuss implementing and managing HESS within standalone renewable energy power systems. The primary focus is enhancing energy storage efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness in these systems isolated from main power grids.

Key points deriving from the literature review include:

HESS as a Solution: emphasis that hybrid systems combining high-energy and high-power storage solutions are more effective for managing the inconsistent output from renewable energy sources, typically associated with standalone systems. This approach extends the life of ESS, reduces costs, and enhances overall system performance.

ESS: Various energy storage technologies, including their technical and economic characteristics, are reviewed to assess their suitability for specific roles within HESS. Decision matrices are introduced to aid in selecting appropriate technologies based on needs.

Control Strategies: The article reviews classical and intelligent control strategies for managing the power flow within renewable energy power systems equipped with HESS. It highlights the future trends in control strategies that might include more complex algorithms capable of improving system response to variable conditions. The concept of control strategy for HESS is illustrated in [Figure 2](#) adopted by [11].

Figure 2. Concept of control strategy for HESS [11].

Future Trends: Predictions for the future of HESS in renewable energy power systems include advancements in control strategies and the integration of predictive models that account for renewable outputs and load demands. This is intended to optimize system efficiency and minimize operational costs.

Authors in [11] provide a comprehensive overview of current technologies and strategies for optimizing standalone renewable energy systems using hybrid storage solutions, focusing on technical viability and cost-efficiency. As this study concludes, various control schemes exist for HESS, addressing power and energy distribution between the storage units. Exploring the potential higher performance and characteristics for appropriate battery size within its application is essential.

With this intention, several control approaches can be found in the literature. These can be classified into three main categories [12,13], as shown in [Figure 3](#):

- Centralized
- Distributed
- Decentralized

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 3. Diagram of the control structure for HESS: (a) Centralized, (b) Distributed, (c) Decentralized adopted by [12].

Centralized Control: In a centralized control system, a single central entity or control centre makes all decisions regarding energy storage operations. This central entity typically has access to a comprehensive view of the entire energy system, including supply, demand, and grid conditions. Decisions regarding when to charge or discharge energy storage assets, how much energy to store or release, and other operational parameters are determined centrally. Centralised control can efficiently coordinate and optimise energy storage resources across the entire system, maximising benefits such as cost savings, grid stability, and renewable energy integration. However, it may also face challenges related to scalability, communication latency, and vulnerability to single points of failure. Examples of this control are Filter-based control, fuzzy logic, rule-based, model predictive control, optimisation, and artificial neural networks.

Decentralized Control: Decentralized control distributes decision-making authority across multiple entities or subsystems within the energy system. Instead of relying on a single central entity, control decisions may be made by individual energy storage assets, local controllers, or distributed energy management systems (EMS). Each entity or subsystem may have limited knowledge of the overall system state but makes decisions based on local information and objectives. Decentralized control can offer greater resilience to failures and scalability by reducing dependence on a single control centre. However, coordination and optimization across the entire system may be less efficient than centralized control, potentially leading to suboptimal performance and increased complexity. This type of control includes Droop-based control, reinforcement learning (RL) and high/low pass filters.

Distributed Hybrid Control: Distributed hybrid control combines elements of both centralized and decentralized control approaches. In this approach, decision-making authority is

distributed across multiple levels of control, with some decisions made centrally and others made locally. Centralized control may handle high-level coordination and optimization tasks, such as long-term planning and system-wide resource allocation. Local controllers or distributed EMSs may handle day-to-day operational tasks, such as real-time control of individual energy storage assets and responding to local grid conditions. Distributed hybrid control aims to leverage the strengths of both centralized and decentralized approaches, balancing efficiency, scalability, and resilience. However, designing and implementing such control systems can be complex, requiring carefully integrating different control strategies and coordination mechanisms. Examples of this type of control are the Consensus algorithm and multi-agent methods [12].

In the concept of operational control, authors in [14] address the thermal aspects often overlooked in vanadium battery modelling. Authors provide a tool for better planning and operational control of ESS in renewable energy applications. Moreover, authors in [15] discussed the benefits of HESS, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Benefits of HESS [15].

These benefits are:

- Minimizes the initial cost contrasted with a single ESS (due to the decoupling of power and energy, the secondary storage system has to cover only the average demand for power).
- Enhances overall system efficiency.
- Improves storage capacity and the lifetime of the plant (minimizes the dynamic stress of the secondary storage system and optimizes the operation) [15].

The authors in [15] explore various control strategies, from classical approaches like droop control to advanced intelligent techniques such as model predictive controllers and neural networks. Each method's benefits and limitations are analysed to provide insights into its practical applications, as shown in Figure 5. Moreover, they emphasize the need for technological advancements, supportive policies, and increased market penetration to realize the potential of hybrid storage solutions fully.

Figure 5. Classification of HESS control techniques [15].

In addition to control strategies, sizing techniques for BESS are crucial for optimizing system performance. Each technique is characterized by its unique advantages and limitations. Figure 6 outlines various methodologies for determining the optimal size of BESS [13].

Figure 6. Sizing techniques of BESS data collected from [13].

Probabilistic Methods: These methods utilise the stochastic nature of renewable energy sources like solar and wind to estimate the optimal battery size and one of the most straightforward approaches to battery sizing. These methods rely less on extensive data, making them suitable for situations with limited information. However, they often optimise a limited number of criteria, which may restrict their use in detailed design processes. Techniques like Monte Carlo simulations are commonly used, generating numerous scenarios to determine the best configuration but requiring significant computational resources. The flowchart is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Flowchart of probabilistic methods collected from [13].

Analytical Methods: Analytical or deterministic methods involve analysing various power system configurations against performance criteria to determine the optimal battery size. They are one of the most broadly used methodologies for BESS size determination. These methods can range from simple calculations to complex simulations over fixed intervals. They are widely used for their straightforwardness but may require extensive computational efforts, especially when dealing with many simulations to achieve high accuracy. Figure 8 shows the flowchart of these methods.

Figure 8. Flowchart of analytical methods collected from [13].

Directed Search-Based Methods: These methods aim to find the optimal solution more efficiently by reducing the number of simulations needed. They are divided into mathematical optimization techniques, which use properties of the solution space, and heuristic techniques, which employ nature-inspired algorithms for a more efficient search. While these methods can improve computational efficiency, they may still struggle with complex non-linear problems. [Figure 9](#) illustrates the flowchart of these methods to help us visualize how they work.

Figure 9. Flowchart of direct search-based methods collected from [13].

Hybrid Methods: These methods combine the strengths of various approaches to overcome their limitations, enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of the optimization process. These methods can be decoupled with two separate optimization processes or coupled, where two methods work together. Hybrid methods aim to achieve a more robust solution and ensure a global optimum with the desired resolution, adapting to the complexities of battery sizing in renewable energy systems [13].

In the literature, the article [16] explores power management strategies for HESS combining vanadium redox flow batteries and supercapacitors. This study focuses on integrating these two storage technologies to enhance overall system performance and cost-effectiveness. Vanadium batteries are known for decoupling energy and power ratings but struggle with high power densities. Conversely, supercapacitors offer high power density and cyclability, making them ideal for managing rapid power fluctuations and high load demands. The research assesses various power management strategies within an active parallel HESS topology, including filtration-based, rule-based, and fuzzy logic techniques.

The study's findings suggest that the fuzzy logic-based technique performs better than others to optimize the use of the supercapacitor stack, leading to reduced operational costs and improved system efficiency. The article highlights the critical role of advanced EMS in maximizing the benefits of hybrid storage solutions, especially in settings where both high energy and high power are required simultaneously. This research contributes to the field by demonstrating how strategic management of vanadium flow batteries and supercapacitors

can lead to more reliable, efficient, and cost-effective energy storage solutions [16]. Authors in [17] outline a novel rule-based strategy for managing power distribution between batteries and ultracapacitors in hybrid electric vehicles. This strategy aims to optimize operational efficiency and extend the lifespan of ESS by reducing the frequency of high C-rate currents drawn from batteries, particularly during sudden acceleration events.

The proposed strategy incorporates a three-stage rule-based controller based on the SOC of the energy sources, the power request direction, and the charge/discharge states. This controller ensures the SOC remains within specified limits, optimising the storage systems' performance and durability. The strategy's efficacy was validated through simulations on a hybrid electric city bus in MATLAB/Simulink, demonstrating significant improvements over traditional systems and alternative approaches. It resulted in smoother changes in battery currents and reduced battery stress compared to systems that do not integrate ultracapacitors.

Overall, the article highlights the potential of rule-based power management to enhance the operational dynamics of hybrid electric vehicles, emphasizing the strategic integration of ultracapacitors to alleviate the load on batteries and improve overall vehicle performance and energy efficiency [17].

Moreover, authors in [18] propose an EMS for electric vehicles that incorporates battery aging considerations, utilizing imitation Q-learning. The primary objective is to enhance electric vehicles' energy efficiency while minimising their batteries' degradation, which is crucial for improving their longevity and performance. The study presents a novel imitation of Q-learning-based EMS that strategically manages power distribution between batteries and supercapacitors in HESS electric vehicles. This approach aims to leverage supercapacitors' high-power density and batteries' high energy density to optimize vehicle performance and reduce battery wear. Key findings from the research indicate that using this imitation Q-learning approach can reduce battery degradation compared to traditional methods. These improvements are attributed to the smarter allocation of energy demands between the battery and supercapacitor, which helps mitigate the rapid discharge and charge cycles that typically accelerate battery aging. Another article by [19] introduces a novel optimal energy management strategy that effectively coordinates a hybrid renewable energy system incorporating offshore wind, marine current, batteries, and ultracapacitors. This research demonstrates the practicality and effectiveness of such hybrid systems in real-world settings, paving the way for future innovations in energy management and the broader adoption of renewable energy solutions. Overall, the study demonstrates the potential of advanced EMS in enhancing the performance and reliability of hybrid renewable energy systems, highlighting significant contributions to renewable energy technology.

Additionally, the primary objectives of the article [20] involve developing and evaluating a model predictive control strategy intended to enhance the operational efficacy of HESS within DC microgrids. The core issue addressed by the authors is the limitation posed by traditional filtration-based power/current allocation strategies, which often results in the discontinuous operation of supercapacitors and affects the overall system stability and performance. The research demonstrates that the proposed model predictive control strategy ensures the supercapacitor's stable and continuous operation and allows the grid-forming HESS to operate more efficiently under large constant power loads. This is achieved by maintaining the SOC within a predefined range, thus preventing frequent mode switching and promoting better transient response and voltage stability [20]. Another study [21] presents an electrical equivalent circuit model for a 3.6 kW vanadium battery, factoring in the effects of flow rate and pump power losses, which are significant in the vanadium battery's operational efficiency. A control methodology for accurately estimating the SOC is proposed. This

methodology is crucial for preventing overcharging or deep discharging, which significantly affects battery life and performance, as the authors discussed in their study. Moreover, the article [22] introduces a new approach to evaluating HESS for grid applications through multi-timescale analysis. The key objective is to harness the distinct advantages of different storage technologies, such as vanadium redox flow batteries and supercapacitors, to improve grid stability, reliability, and power quality, often impacted by the variable nature of renewable energy sources. The methodology uses mathematical criteria like frequency, power transients, and power peaks to develop classification thresholds for EMS across different time scales. The paper highlights the importance of HESS in offering versatile and dynamic solutions for energy management in grid applications, where the integration of vanadium and supercapacitor batteries can provide rapid response capabilities and handle high-power peaks efficiently. This is particularly useful in scenarios such as peak shaving in industrial settings and enhancing the operational efficiency of renewable energy systems within distribution grids. Experimental load profiles from various applications, including municipal, airport, and industrial setups, are analysed to demonstrate the proposed classification system's practical application. The study suggests that combining the capabilities of vanadium and supercapacitor batteries within a HESS can significantly extend service life, enhance safety, and utilize non-critical raw materials more effectively than traditional single storage solutions. In summary, this research advances understanding HESS optimization in grid applications. It establishes a foundation for future innovations in energy storage technology by developing an open-source database for load profiles and a framework for EMS tailored to hybrid storage solutions [22].

However, the importance of using machine learning techniques is discussed in the literature, for exploring energy management strategies in HESS. For instance, in article [23] the authors present a compelling case for integrating batteries and ultracapacitors, utilizing reinforcement learning (RL) to optimize system efficiency and longevity. This innovative approach addresses critical safety risks, such as thermal runaway and rapid deterioration of battery performance under high traction power impacts. Unlike traditional rule-based and optimization-based control methods, which often struggle with flexibility and real-time applicability, the RL method is depicted as dynamically adapting to operational conditions without requiring exhaustive system models. The findings indicate significant reductions in energy loss and effective maintenance of the battery's SOC, which are crucial for minimizing operational costs and enhancing the sustainability of energy systems in vehicles. Furthermore, the study's methodology distinguishes it in the current research landscape by demonstrating how artificial intelligence can lead to more robust and economically viable energy management solutions. This aligns with broader industry trends towards intelligent, adaptive systems that promise to revolutionize energy strategies in transportation. The article not only advances the understanding of HESS but also underscores the potential of machine learning in overcoming traditional challenges in energy management, paving the way for future investigations into more efficient and adaptable technologies. Additionally, the practical implications of these findings suggest that RL could play a pivotal role in developing next-generation smart grids and sustainable transport solutions, further solidifying its place as a transformative force in energy systems engineering [23]. Another article [24] introduces a novel approach to EMS in electric vehicles with HESS, comprising batteries and supercapacitors. The main objective is to optimize the power allocation between these storage units under varying driving conditions, thereby minimizing battery capacity loss and power loss costs. The core strategy involves employing deep RL, particularly a proximal policy optimization approach, enhanced with an incentive reward function. This function prioritizes the use of the supercapacitor during high load conditions, which aids in rapid learning of optimal power management strategies. The implementation also includes a method for pre-training the learning agent using a velocity transfer probability surface

derived from standard driving cycles. This feature helps maintain strategy optimality even in unfamiliar driving scenarios. This study highlights the potential of integrating advanced learning algorithms with incentive mechanisms to enhance EMS efficiency and sustainability in electric vehicles [24].

Furthermore, authors in [25] propose an innovative RL-based online optimal control method tailored for HESS in AC-DC microgrids, including photovoltaic systems and diesel generators. This method aims to address the problem of disturbances caused by conventional unregulated charging and discharging of energy storage in microgrids, which can degrade power quality and overall system performance. The method significantly enhances system stability and operational efficiency by employing neural networks to estimate the nonlinear dynamics of HESS and to learn the optimal control inputs adaptively. The RL-based online optimal control method is fully decentralized, requires only local measurements, and is designed to be plug-and-play, enhancing the integration and functionality of HESS in both islanded and grid-tied operational modes. The paper substantiates the effectiveness of this approach through extensive simulations and experiments, demonstrating its superiority in maintaining system stability and improving transient performance compared to traditional control methods. The conclusion emphasizes the potential of the RL-based online optimal method to significantly optimize the charging and discharging processes of HESS, thereby mitigating disturbances and enhancing the resilience of microgrids [25].

Another study [26] discussed RL-based approaches to energy management of HESS in electric vehicles. HESS, which combines different energy storage technologies like batteries and ultracapacitors, aims to improve the performance and lifespan of electric vehicles batteries. Traditional EMS, including rule-based and optimization methods, face challenges with dynamic and complex energy demands for electric vehicles. This study emphasizes the potential of RL algorithms to address these issues, providing a promising alternative for real-time, adaptive energy management. The general framework of RL-based EMS of HESS is shown in [Figure 10](#).

Figure 10. The general framework of an RL-based EMS of HESS was adopted by [26].

By leveraging the interactions between the vehicle and its environment, RL adjusts the power distribution among the storage components to optimize efficiency and battery life. This approach adapts to varying driving conditions and enhances decision-making over time, unlike traditional methods, which may not dynamically respond to changes in energy demand or driving scenarios. The paper reviews various RL strategies, discussing their advantages in learning optimal control policies without prior system models and highlighting their efficacy in managing HESS in electric vehicles through multiple examples from the literature. A summary of the different aspects of RL-based EMSs is illustrated in [Figure 11](#) below.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Author(s)	Power split	Algorithm	States (s_t)	Actions (a_t)	Reward (r_t)
Yue et al. (2014) [30]	UC and Li-ion batteries	TD(λ)	$s = \{P_{tot}, v, \hat{v}', V_{UC}^{OC}, V_{DC}\}$ v : vehicle speed, \hat{v}' : Predicted vehicle acceleration, V_{UC}^{OC} : UC open circuit voltage, DC bus voltage	$a = \{I_{c,b}, I_{a,b}\}$ $I_{a,b}$: battery bank discharge, $I_{c,b}$: battery bank charge current	$r = - \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} V_b^{OC}(t) I_a(t) dt - \frac{1}{2} C_s \left[(V_{UC}^{OC}(t_{k-1}))^2 - (V_{UC}^{OC}(t_k))^2 \right]$
Hsu et al. (2016) [31]	Fuel cell and battery	Q-learning	$s = \{SoC_b, \text{pedal position}\}$ SoC_b : state of charge of battery	$a = \left\{ \frac{P_{FC2M}(t)}{P_{demand}(t)} \right\}$ $P_{FC2M}(t)$: motor power supplied by the fuel cell, $P_{demand}(t)$: consumed power	$r_{soc} = \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{soc}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta SoC(t)^2}{2\sigma_{soc}^2}\right)$ $r_{eco} = \begin{cases} \frac{k_2}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{eco}} \exp\left(-\frac{(P_{FC}(t)/P_{FCmax})^2}{2\sigma_{eco}^2}\right), & SoC < SoC_L \\ \frac{k_2}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{eco}} \exp\left(-\frac{\left(1 - \frac{\eta_{FC} P_{FC}(t)}{P_{FCmax}\eta_{FCmax}}\right)^2}{2\sigma_{eco}^2}\right), & otherwise \end{cases}$
Cao and Xiong (2017) [32]	Battery and UC	Q-learning	$s = \{P, SoC_b, SoV_{UC}\}$ P : Power	$a = \{I_b\}$ I_b : Battery current	The reward function is defined based on the energy loss of HESS that includes the loss of the battery pack, the UC pack and the DC/DC converter
Xiong et al. (2018) [33]	Battery and UC	Q-learning	$s = \{P, SoC_b, SoV_{UC}\}$	$a = \{I_b\}$	$r = \{Loss_b(t) + Loss_{UC}(t) + Loss_{acdc}(t)\}$
Xiong et al. (2018) [9]	Battery and UC	Q-learning	$s = \{P, SoC_b, SoV_{UC}\}$	$a = \{I_b\}$	The reward function is defined based on the energy loss of HESS
Ye et al. (2021) [36]	Battery and UC	Q-learning	$s = \{v, T_{demand}\}$	$a = \{P_{UC}\}$	$r = -\omega(E_{bat} + E_{UC}) - (1 - \omega)Q_{loss} + \beta$ ω : weight factor to control the trade-off between energy saving and battery aging, β : a bias constant
Xu et al. (2022) [38]	Battery and UC	Soft actor-critic (SAC)	$s = \{P_{demand}, SoC_b, SoC_{UC}\}$	$a = \{P_b\}$	$r = \frac{1000}{E_{loss}} - (SoC_b(t_0) - SoC_b(t))^2 - 4(SoC_{UC}(t_0) - SoC_{UC}(t))^2$
Fu et al. (2022) [8]	Fuel cell, battery and UC	Deep Q-learning	$s = \{SoC_{UC}, SoC_b, v, P_{demand}, P_{UC}, P_b\}$	$a = \{P_{FC}/P_b\}$	$r = H(t) + \beta(\Delta SoC)^2$ β : Transition coefficient, $H(t)$: Hydrogen consumption, ΔSoC : deviation between current SoC of battery and benchmark
Yang et al. (2023)	Engine-generator set (EGS), battery, and UC	Multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL)	$s = \{v, SoC_b, SoV_{UC}\}$	EGS agent: $a = \{\omega_e, T_g\}$ ω_e : Engine rotational speed, T_g : generator torque HESS agent: $a = \{P_b\}$	$r^1 = \begin{cases} -\dot{m}_f, & otherwise \\ R_{pen}^1, & \text{if } SoC_b \text{ violates constraint} \end{cases}$ $r^2 = \begin{cases} -(SoC_b - SoC_b^{pre})^2 - \beta \Delta SoC , & otherwise \\ R_{pen}^2, & \text{if } SoC_{UC} \text{ violates constraint} \end{cases}$ R_{pen} : Negative constant

Figure 11. Summary of different aspects of RL-based EMS in HESS by [26].

In conclusion, RL-based EMS offers significant improvements in managing the complexities of HESS in electric vehicles, promising enhanced vehicle performance, longer battery life, and better adaptability to driving conditions. Future research directions include advancing RL techniques and exploring their practical applications under varied driving and environmental conditions to validate their robustness and effectiveness [26]. Moreover, the article by [27] focuses on developing RL real-time power management strategy for HESS in plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. The primary objective is to optimize the power distribution between the battery and the ultracapacitor to minimize energy loss, enhance system efficiency, and improve battery health by effectively managing the discharge and charging cycles. The study introduces a real-time power management strategy that employs RL algorithms to dynamically adjust power allocations based on current driving conditions and energy storage states. The approach is tested under various conditions, including different temperatures, states of health, initial SOC, and driving cycles, demonstrating its adaptability and robustness. The outcomes reveal that the reinforcement learning-based strategy not only reduces total energy loss compared to conventional rule-based methods but also effectively manages the battery's charging and discharging activities. This results in prolonged battery life and improved overall system performance, proving that the proposed method is more efficient and adaptable to different operating conditions and driving patterns [27]. Another article by [28] discusses the optimal planning of HESS using curtailed renewable energy through deep RL. The main goal is to improve energy management by efficiently utilizing excess renewable energy that is otherwise curtailed due to oversupply. The research emphasizes using advanced RL techniques to handle the complexities and

uncertainties involved in large-scale EMS, which traditional mathematical programming methods can be struggle with. In essence, this study's outcomes highlight the potential of deep RL to enhance decision-making in energy storage and management, enabling more effective integration of renewable energy sources into the power grid. This approach not only helps reduce energy wastage through curtailment but also contributes to a more sustainable and efficient energy management framework [28].

In another article [29], the primary goal in discussing the SimSES (Simulation Stationary ESS) simulation framework is to introduce a sophisticated tool for modelling and evaluating stationary ESS, emphasizing its comprehensive technical performance and economic assessment coverage. The framework supports a variety of energy storage technologies, including lithium-ion batteries, redox flow batteries, and hydrogen storage systems. It offers detailed models that elucidate their operational dynamics and degradation behaviours. Additionally, SimSES incorporates advanced thermal modelling capabilities and diverse power electronics configurations and can simulate various applications such as peak shaving and frequency containment reserve.

The article concludes that SimSES is an exceptionally versatile and effective tool for the detailed simulation and analysis of ESS. It aids in evaluating the technical performance and economic feasibility across different storage configurations and operational strategies. The presented case studies demonstrate the framework's ability to analyse scenarios effectively, showing that hybrid systems and specific setups, such as cascaded converters, can significantly optimize system efficiency and economic outcomes.

Notable features of the framework include its open-source nature, which encourages community involvement and ongoing improvement. SimSES's modularity and adaptability allow for the easy integration of new models and technologies, making it applicable to various uses. This flexibility ensures that SimSES remains an invaluable resource for researchers, engineers, and policymakers involved in designing, implementing, and evaluating ESS. Furthermore, the growing importance of HESS across various applications like charging stations, grid services, and microgrids is discussed in [29]. HESSs integrate multiple types of ESSs to enhance overall performance by leveraging the strengths of each system to improve efficiency and lifespan. This study aims to comprehensively analyse Redox-Flow Batteries' performance and integration within HESSs, highlighting their benefits, particularly for stationary storage applications.

The methodology involves a detailed evaluation of the key performance indicators for different ESSs suitable for hybridization with vanadium batteries. It proposes an optimal coupling architecture of HESSs, including vanadium and supercapacitor batteries. This is assessed through numerical simulations and an in-depth analysis of various EMS for potential application scenarios, focusing on control and optimization strategies. [Figure 12](#) shows the real-time optimization management of EMS for HESS.

Figure 12. Shows the architecture of the energy management system in real-time [30].

The EMS process for HESS involves three critical steps:

Prediction: This step uses historical data, like renewable energy production and weather conditions, to forecast vital parameters such as load demand and supply. This predictive modelling helps in planning and adjusting energy management strategies accordingly.

Optimization: In this step, the data predicted is used along with system parameters and regulatory requirements to create an optimized operation strategy for the HESS. This involves calculating the most efficient way to utilise the storage and generation capacity of the system.

Implementation and Evaluation: After the optimization, the HESS components implement the strategy. Following implementation, there is an evaluation and improvement phase to determine whether the EMS objectives have been met and to assess any necessary adjustments to improve system performance.

The EMS uses advanced control techniques, potentially including artificial intelligence, to manage these processes efficiently. This architecture ensures that the HESS operates effectively, balancing energy production, storage, and consumption needs while considering external factors and internal system capabilities.

This study's conclusion underscores the significant advantages of using HESSs, particularly those incorporating vanadium batteries, to enhance the efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and durability of ESS. The research demonstrates that optimal system design and effective management strategies are crucial in maximizing the benefits of hybrid energy storage solutions, providing valuable insights for future enhancements in energy storage technology [30].

Furthermore, in the existing literature on HESS sizing, a multi-objective model was presented in [31], aiming for the best HESS configuration that maximizes grid output stability and minimizes HESS investment. Günther et al. [6] introduced a theoretical approach to combine two storage technologies with different specific powers to create HESS that matches application requirements and reduces overall storage size. The authors have offered a broad perspective on HESS, examining dimensioning issues without being tied to specific technologies, control strategies, or applications. Moreover, they emphasized that any storage system can be split into base and peak storage, each defined by energy and power capacities. The specific powers of the two storages can be calculated by dividing power capacity into energy capacity [7,10]. The particular power is a fixed value for most storage technologies, which is similar to the C-rate, generally used for the characteristics of batteries [6]. Günther et al. [6] described the hybridization model and dimensioning and provided a tool to visualise the hybridization curve in MATLAB. However, this theoretical model has some limitations that might directly impact real-world use. As the authors mention, the SOC must begin and finish at zero for each cycle. Additionally, the signal's arithmetic mean should be zero. In practice, these conditions are challenging to obtain.

This report's second chapter addresses the literature gap on hybrid battery sizing models and their practical limitations. It proposes a model designed for general applicability with real-life data. This model is offered as open source and facilitates testing, application, and enhancement. It comprises three parts: analysing user input data to identify recurring patterns, determining optimal dispatch to maximize energy delivery, and identifying optimal configurations for hybrid battery solutions.

1.2 Multi-Service Strategy in Hybridization Approaches

In the realm of modern technology and business operations, the concept of hybridization has emerged as a strategic imperative for organizations seeking to optimize their service delivery models. Hybridization, particularly in the context of multi-service strategies, represents a dynamic approach to meeting diverse consumer demands, leveraging a combination of traditional and digital channels, as well as various service delivery mechanisms. This introduction delves into the significance of multi-service strategy within hybridization approaches, exploring how organizations navigate the complexities of integrating different service offerings to enhance customer experiences, operational efficiency, and competitive advantage.

In an increasingly interconnected and digitized world, consumers expect seamless access to a spectrum of services across multiple platforms. This expectation has driven organizations to adopt hybridization approaches, which blend conventional service delivery methods with innovative digital solutions. The advent of technologies such as cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things has catalysed this shift, enabling businesses to offer a diverse array of services tailored to individual preferences and needs.

Energy plays a crucial role in enriching the quality of life and bolstering economic prosperity. Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognize that the energy sector presently makes a substantial contribution to greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, attaining climate neutrality in Spain, the European Union (EU), and worldwide requires a profound overhaul of the energy system [32].

The European Climate Law, enacted in June 2021, represents a landmark moment by establishing and delineating the objective of attaining climate neutrality in the EU by 2050. This legislation also establishes a framework for advancing endeavours to mitigate the impacts of climate change, mandating all Member States to develop adaptation strategies and plans. In 2023, the EU introduced a series of Commission proposals aimed at aligning EU climate, energy, transport, and taxation policies to achieve a net reduction in greenhouse gas emissions of at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels.

In February 2024, the European Commission conducted an evaluation of the EU's 2040 climate target. In its assessment, the Commission recommended a 90% reduction in the EU's net greenhouse gas emissions by 2040 relative to 1990 levels [33–36].

Spain has a Strategic Energy and Climate Framework, which aims to establish measures to facilitate climate change towards a sustainable and competitive economic model. This restructuring of the energy system not only involves decreasing emissions to achieve climate neutrality but also the creation of a more equitable, fair, and competitive model.

This model should reduce external energy dependence, strengthen the security of supply, and mitigate the vulnerability of society and the economy to the volatility of international markets, especially those related to fossil fuels. It should also take advantage of social, environmental, and economic opportunities arising from this transformation.

The key pieces that make up this framework are:

- The Climate Change and Energy Transition Bill
- The National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) 2021-2030
- The Just Transition Strategy.
- The National Fuel Poverty Strategy
- The Long-Term Decarbonization Strategy

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 13. Greenhouse gas emissions 2015-250. Source: European Commission [36].

The PNIEC identifies challenges and opportunities across the five dimensions of the Energy Union: decarbonization, including renewables; energy efficiency; energy security; the internal energy market; and research, innovation, and competitiveness. It aims to advance decarbonization, laying a firm foundation for consolidating a climate-neutral pathway for the economy and society by 2050.

The measures envisaged in the PNIEC will enable the following results to be achieved by 2030:

- 23% reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions compared to 1990.
- 42% of renewable energy as a percentage of final energy use.
- 39.5% improvement in energy efficiency.
- 74% of renewable energy in electricity generation.

In a complementary way, the Long-Term Strategy (LTS) is a flexible instrument to guide the economic and energy transformation toward climate neutrality by mid-century. This LTS aims to articulate a coherent and integrated response to the climate crisis that seizes opportunities for the modernization and competitiveness of our economy and is socially just and inclusive. It is a roadmap for climate neutrality by 2050, with intermediate milestones in 2030 and 2040.

It aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To reach a 97% share of renewable energies in the final energy mix.
- To make the electricity sector 100% renewable.
- Reduce energy dependence on foreign energy from 73% to 13%, achieving savings of 344,000 million euros.
- Electrify more than 50% of the economy by installing around 250 GW of renewable power.
- Developing renewable hydrogen and renewable fuels.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

- Mitigate and promote carbon sinks that will achieve climate neutrality with a 90% reduction in emissions compared to 1990.

Figure 14. LTS main goals. Source: ELP.

Through the LTS and the PNIEC, the medium (2030) and long-term (2050) are integrated, providing credibility, climate commitment, and industrial opportunities, as part of a single strategic vision for Spain. These results will allow progress towards meeting the longer-term objective that has guided the preparation of this Plan, which is to achieve GHG emission neutrality in Spain by 2050, in line with the positions adopted by the European Commission and most Member States [4]-[5].

Figure 15. Long-term Decarbonisation Strategy. Source: ELP.

In this way more and more renewables have to be incorporated in the future modern power system.

The evolution of modern power grids demands a paradigm shift towards multi-service functionality to effectively address the diverse and dynamic challenges of the energy landscape. Traditional approaches to energy storage, often centered around standalone BESS, face inherent limitations in efficiently balancing the complex interplay between power and energy requirements.

As the demand for grid stability, renewable energy integration, and operational flexibility intensifies, there arises a critical need for innovative solutions that can optimize multi-service functionality within the energy sector [37,38].

Multi-service strategy lies at the core of hybridization approaches, providing organizations with the flexibility to adapt to evolving market dynamics and consumer behaviours. By offering a comprehensive suite of services encompassing both traditional and digital channels, businesses can cater to a broader customer base while capitalizing on emerging opportunities in the digital ecosystem. Moreover, a well-executed multi-service strategy fosters synergies between different service lines, driving operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

However, implementing a successful multi-service strategy within a hybridization framework is not without its challenges. Organizations must contend with issues such as interoperability, data integration, and cybersecurity risks, as they seek to harmonize disparate service offerings into a cohesive ecosystem. Moreover, maintaining consistency in service quality and ensuring a seamless user experience across various touchpoints requires careful planning and strategic alignment.

Despite these challenges, the rewards of embracing multi-service strategy in hybridization approaches are considerable. By leveraging the strengths of both traditional and digital service channels, organizations can unlock new revenue streams, deepen customer engagement, and differentiate themselves in competitive markets. Moreover, a robust multi-service strategy business to anticipate and respond effectively to evolving consumer preferences and market trends, thereby sustaining long-term growth and resilience.

In summary, the integration of multi-service strategy within hybridization approaches represents a strategic imperative for organizations seeking to thrive in today's dynamic business landscape. By embracing the convergence of traditional and digital service delivery methods, businesses can unlock new opportunities for innovation, growth, and competitive advantage, while delivering enhanced value to their customers.

2 Hybrid Energy Storage System Sizing Model

This chapter will discuss the proposed methodology for optimal sizing of a HESS. The subsequent section will delve into the sizing model designed explicitly for HESS, utilizing load data from an industrial building involved in the InterSTORE project Portuguese pilot.

2.1 Proposed Methodology

The primary aim of the proposed methodology is to investigate and identify the optimal sizing of a HESS, outperforming a single battery. The model introduces a threefold contribution,

illustrated diagrammatically in [Figure 16](#). This figure provides a step-by-step visualization of the hybridization model's workflow, offering a clear overview of our approach.

Figure 16. Hybridization model approach.

The proposed hybridization approach consists of three main steps. The initial step is to identify and analyse recurring patterns using a building from the UC05 pilot in Portugal as a practical case study. This serves to assess the model's performance and applicability. The findings from this step will then be used as inputs for the subsequent steps.

The second step conducts a battery scheduling optimization, providing the median dispatch. Initially, a set of requirements and constraints that the HESS sizing model must satisfy are established. This HESS aims to meet specific application requirements more effectively than a single battery system by:

- Adjusting the power-to-energy ratio of the two storages results in a HESS with a specific power profile that aligns closely with the application's needs.
- Reducing the overall system size compared to a single-storage solution, thereby lowering costs while maintaining the original total energy and power capacities.
- Minimizing idle power or capacity ensures that most of the power and energy are utilized, thus maximizing the battery's energy output.
- The system is designed to start and finish at the same State of Charge (SOC), ensuring efficient energy use.
- Accommodating different dispatch goals by incorporating various optimization functions allows for tailored energy management strategies.

The third step focuses on the battery optimal hybrid identification area, which uses the battery dispatch, power, and energy capacity derived from the preceding step. This step provides a mathematical split according to cut-off values assigned to the dispatch signal to obtain a hybridization curve, supporting the decision-making of the HESS configuration. The hybrid curve outlines an optimal region for decision-making to offer flexible and several configuration options aligning to viable commercial solutions and not only a mere output of a mathematical exercise.

2.2 Recurring Pattern Identification

This section will discuss the first step of the proposed model, which focuses on identifying and analysing recurring patterns. A comprehensive flowchart detailing this crucial step can be found in [Figure 17](#).

Figure 17. Recurring pattern identification approach.

2.2.1 Generic Load Analysis – InterSTORE PT Pilot example

In the context of UC05, concerning the energy supply for the generic load of an Industrial Building in Portugal, the task is to determine the optimal size of a battery system. This required selecting a dedicated service and determining the demand time. Although multiple services with various performance targets or optimization functions could have been considered, the starting point was to use the battery to support the energy needs of a building. The initial step involved analysing the building's energy consumption patterns to identify the most common pattern. Identifying a recurring pattern is crucial for dispatching the battery effectively; without it, creating an optimal schedule would be impossible due to the unpredictability of consumption. A non-supervised machine learning technique is employed to cluster daily energy usage profiles based on a full year's data to achieve this. This data, capturing energy consumption every 15 minutes, was collected from the industrial building in question throughout the year (from 01/01/2022 to 01/01/2023). The following sections will analyse these data to identify the recurring load pattern.

2.2.2 Dynamic Time Warping Algorithm

Analyzing time series to determine the accurate load profile is critical. Time series analysis by measuring distances among data points and their similarity has been applied before [39]. The two most common distance measures for comparing time series data are the Euclidean and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithms [39–42]. DTW is highly effective as a time-series similarity measure, and efficient at minimizing the impacts of time shifts and distortions [41,42]. Authors in [43] point out the extension of the DTW algorithm to identify recurring

patterns in time series. Moreover, the DTW algorithm can extend and efficiently track and identify recurring patterns in time series, even when these patterns exhibit complex behaviors such as changing frequencies and backward motions [43].

Since Euclidean distance computes the distance between point to point of each time series, which is unsuitable for UC05 data, it would cluster similarities of observations instead of similarities of complete daily profiles regardless of whether they are shifted in time to some degree. DTW is used to find the similarities from a set of time series by minimizing the cumulative distance between aligned points. Agglomerative hierarchical clustering is preferred over K-means clustering because it is better suited for analyzing load profiles [44–47] and provides a more visually intuitive representation to understand data grouping [48]. The basic DTW algorithm uses a dynamic programming approach to compute the optimal alignment and minimum distance. The optimization function can be defined as follows:

Let $D(i, j)$ be the accumulated distance between the i^{th} element of sequence A and the j^{th} element of sequence B. Then, the optimization function $D(i, j)$ can be recursively defined as Equation 1:

$$D(i, j) = d(a_i, b_j) + \min(D(i-1, j), D(i, j-1), D(i-1, j-1)) \quad (1)$$

where:

$d(a_i, b_j)$ is the distance between elements a_j . and b_j .

$D(i-1, j)$ represents the accumulated distance from the previous element in sequence A.

$D(i, j-1)$ represents the accumulated distance from the previous elements in sequence B.

$D(i-1, j-1)$ represents the accumulated distance from the previous elements in both sequences.

Following the data collection, a data series of pre-processing steps to prepare the dataset for recurring pattern analysis were taken. Initially, we excluded abnormal days, such as New Year's Day and Christmas Day (1st of January and 25th of December). To address missing values, we identified NaN entries and adopted a forward-fill approach. The remaining 363 days were individualized as daily consumption profiles, each with 96 observations (15-minute observations). Moreover, we applied to the data the 'standard-scaler' technique from the 'scikit-learn' library to standardize and normalize the data in Python. With the data in their standardized form, a distance matrix using the DTW algorithm was calculated. The matrix represents the pairwise DTW distances between data signals. It computes the DTW distance for each pair of signals using the 'dtw' function in Python.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of DTW for aligning daily load curves in this dataset, two daily loads were selected to compare the DTW with Euclidean distance measures shown in [Figure 18](#). This comparison highlights Despite temporal shifts, DTW's superior ability to match similar patterns in one point with all other points is a crucial advantage over Euclidean distance's more inflexible point-to-point analysis.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 18. Differences between Euclidean and DTW algorithms from two daily load profiles.

2.2.3 Clustering Algorithm

The matrix of the pairwise DTW distances is considered for the hierarchical clustering of the time series data. The linkage matrix was computed using a single linkage approach based on the distance matrix [49]. The single linkage approach is an agglomerative method that begins by treating each data point as a separate cluster and then iteratively merges clusters with the smallest minimum distance between any of their points. The analysis pinpointed the centroid index associated with the minimum distance, identifying the closest time series within each cluster. A dendrogram is provided to visually represent the hierarchical structure of the clusters derived from the DTW algorithm and linkage matrix with a highlighting threshold with a highlighting blue threshold line, all shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Dendrogram of 363 data points.

Building on the previous steps and based on the threshold line, the specific level (Level-4) was defined to highlight the data points assigned to the clusters based on the distance threshold. So, to reach the most recurring pattern cluster with the most data points, the data was counted and stored in descending order into their unique clusters to have a clearer

picture of the top clusters with the most data points. As a result, the cluster with the most representative recurring pattern was identified based on the highest count, as illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Identify the most representative recurring pattern.

In this comprehensive clustering analysis, we found that Cluster 11 has 210 data points, Cluster 12 has 110 data points, Cluster 4 has 16 data points, Cluster 7 has 7 data points, and Cluster 1 has 5 data points. The top clusters collectively account for 348 data points out of 363, with 15 unique clusters identified. The cluster deemed the most recurring pattern based on data point count was Cluster 11, with 210 data points. These insights into cluster formation and the identification of representative clusters are visually represented in Figure 20, showcasing the dendrogram derived from this in-depth analysis in Python.

2.2.4 Load Profile Identification

Upon selecting the most recurring pattern for analysis, a data analytics step is required. Figure 21 offers an examination of the time series within this cluster. No outliers were identified, and to understand the spread of the data, a box plot was considered an effective visualization tool, as shown in Figure 21(a). Focusing on the most representative cluster (Cluster 11) provides a box plot for the time series within that cluster. This plot offers insights into the data's distribution, variability, and central tendency [50]. By analysing the box plots for Cluster 11, we gained a deeper understanding of its load pattern and trend. The second step was to define the load profile for Cluster 11, and we examined the median pattern from the 210-time series, which effectively represents the cluster's median behaviour. We also determined the peak power demand by assessing the maximum load power (232 kW) from the box plot across these time series. This study ascertained the minimum power from the minimum load power value (31 kW), presented in Figure 21(b). At this point, the maximum power value to be considered in the next step can be multiplied by a coefficient k to provide some slack to the battery's maximum rated power. This can be applied to avoid operating at a 100% load factor when such maximum demand occurs. In the example provided, we've applied an 8% slack, corresponding to 250 kW of maximum rated power.

Figure 21. (a) Box plot of 210 data points in a recurring pattern; (b) determine the median of the load profile.

The median, unaffected by extreme outliers, reveals the standard load pattern. Over a span of 24 hours, these median load values profile represented in each hour (h) are [32.0, 31.0, 32.0, 31.0, 31.0, 31.0, 38.5, 57.0, 76.0, 121.5, 171.0, 155.0, 117.5, 92.0, 90.0, 108.0, 96.5, 88.0, 78.0, 67.0, 48.0, 39.0, 34.0, 33.0], which allowed the calculation of the total energy demand given by $E_{(Total\ Demand)}$ of 1698 kWh, seen in Equation 2.

$$E_{(Total\ Demand)} = \sum_{t=0}^{23} P_{load}(t) \quad (2)$$

This load profile, derived from Cluster 11, will serve as an input for the subsequent model selection. The insights and recurring pattern analysis here will be used in the analyses and decisions in the following part of our study.

2.3 Battery Optimization Scheduling

The model proposed in this chapter allows for flexibility at each step, enabling substitution with alternative methods or customization with specific data based on the requirements of each input step. In this section, two optimization model approaches will be introduced to show how the hybridization model will work in the next section. The output of this section will be the dispatch of the battery.

2.3.1 Optimization Model

This second step of the sizing methodology receives inputs from the recurring pattern (load diagram) of the previous step. It dispatches the battery system for the following day (or other defined time window). To do so, apart from the load diagram itself, it takes as an input the in kW (multiplied by a slack weight, in our case ~ 8%) of the recurring pattern analysis (seen in the box plot [Figure 21](#) (a)). It considers an initial value of energy capacity (kWh), considered to be a C-rate of 1, hence the same value of power (250 kWh). It then runs an optimization algorithm. The dispatch optimization can be chosen by the user of the model. We provide two options for the sake of clarity and to enrich the example. The first is a maximizing function, maximizing the energy supplied by the battery to the load. The second one is a minimization function to minimize the cost of energy to supply to the used building (load). Others can be used according to the user's needs (minimize surplus, maximize auto-consumption, minimize emissions, etc.).

The first proposed optimization model:

The problem is solved using a linear programming (LP) algorithm, using the library PULP and PuLP's solve () method from Python. The optimization problem is specified in the GitHub code, and it can be described as follows:

Problem Statement:

The optimization sets up a LP problem to maximise the total energy charged into the battery over the day and provide it to a generic load.

Objective Function is shown in Equation 3:

$$\max \sum_{t \in T} E_{in} [t] \Delta t \quad (3)$$

Table 2 describes the variables and constraints considered in the optimization problem.

Table 2. Describes variables and constraints.

Variables	
P_{in}	Power input to the battery at each hour.
P_{out}	Power output from the battery at each hour.
E_{in}	Energy charged by the battery at each hour.
E_{out}	Energy discharged by the battery at each hour.
SOE	State of energy of the battery at the end of each hour.
Charge Discharge	Binary variable representing whether the battery is charging or discharging at each hour.

Constraints	
Energy Balance Constraint	Ensures that the SOE of the battery is correctly updated at each hour based on energy flows.
Power and Energy Capacity Constraints	Ensure that the power input/output and energy charged/discharged do not exceed the battery's capacity limits.
Binary Constraint	Ensures that the battery cannot charge and discharge simultaneously.
Load Constraints	The power output from the battery cannot exceed the load demand at each hour.
SOE Constraints	The SOE is constrained to be the same at the beginning and end of the day (hour 0 and hour 23).

Mathematically, the constraints can be represented as follows from Equations [4-15]:

$$SOE_t = E_{in}(t) - E_{out}(t), t = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$SOE_t = SOE_{t-1} + E_{in}(t) - E_{out}(t), t > 0 \quad (5)$$

$$P_{in}(t) = E_{in}(t), \forall t \in T \quad (6)$$

$$P_{out}(t) = E_{out}(t), \forall t \in T \quad (7)$$

$$P_{in}(t) \leq Max_{energy}, \forall t \in T \quad (8)$$

$$P_{out}(t) \leq Max_{energy}, \forall t \in T \quad (9)$$

$$E_{in}(t) \leq Max_{energy}, \forall t \in T \quad (10)$$

$$E_{out}(t) \leq Max_{energy}, \forall t \in T \quad (11)$$

$$E_{in}(t) \leq Charge - Discharge * Max_{energy}, \forall t \in T \quad (12)$$

$$E_{in}(t) \leq (1 - Charge - Discharge) * Max_{energy}, \forall t \in T \quad (13)$$

$$P_{out}(t) \leq Load, \forall t \in T \quad (14)$$

$$SOC_{t=0} = SOC_{t=23} = 0 \quad (15)$$

The LP for battery optimization scheduling is designed with a clear objective: to maximize the energy supplied to the load by the battery. This goal is encapsulated in the objective function, which aims to maximize the sum of the energy inputs to the battery over the recurring pattern of the day from the previous step and set of constraints. The objective function, as stated in Equation 3, seeks to maximize the total energy $E_{in}(t)$ charged into the battery over the specified time T . Moreover, constraints, detailed in Equations 4 to 15, including the energy balance, power and energy capacity limits, operational logic through binary variables to prevent simultaneous charging and discharging, and load demands to define the dispatch of the battery.

The Second proposed optimization model:

The optimization model under discussion offers a comprehensive framework for the operational management of ESS within a built environment, focusing on dual objectives: minimizing energy supply costs and mitigating environmental impacts. This model extends beyond conventional approaches by integrating the degradation costs of batteries and the environmental footprint of various energy storage technologies. Herein, we delineate the model's structure, objectives, and potential to inform battery dispatch strategies. The model adopts a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) approach conducive to solving problems with continuous and discrete decision variables. Table 3 describes the variables and constraints considered in this optimization problem.

Table 3. Describes variables and constraints.

Variables	
P_t^{abs}	Active power absorption at PCC (kW)
P_t^+	BESS charging active power set point at AC side (kW)
P_t^-	BESS discharging active power set point at AC side (kW)
δ_t^{BESS}	Auxiliary binary variable for non-simultaneity of inverse flows at BESS
δ_t^{PCC}	Auxiliary binary variable for non-simultaneity of inverse flows at PCC
E_t	BESS energy content (kWh)
E_t^{deg}	BESS degraded energy content as a result of a discharge event (Wh)
Parameters	
Δt	Length of time intervals (h)
$\hat{\lambda}_t^{market}$	Forecasted market prices ((€/kWh)
\overline{PCC}^{lim}	Maximum power injection/absorption at the point of common coupling (kW)
\hat{E}^{ini}	BESS initial energy content (kWh)
\bar{E}	BESS maximum energy content (kWh)
\underline{E}	BESS minimum energy content (kWh)
\hat{m}^{deg}	BESS degradation curve linearization slope
$\hat{\eta}^+$	Constant charging efficiency ($\hat{\eta}^+ = \hat{\eta}^{inv} \cdot \hat{\eta}^c$)
$\hat{\eta}^-$	Constant discharging efficiency ($\hat{\eta}^- = \hat{\eta}^{inv} \cdot \hat{\eta}^d$)
$P_{(s)}^{AC,+}$	BESS maximum charging power (inverters' limits) (VA)
$P_{(s)}^{AC,-}$	BESS maximum discharging power (inverters' limits) (VA)
$P_s^{AC,+}$	BESS minimum charging power (inverters' limits) (VA)
$P_s^{AC,-}$	BESS minimum discharging power (inverters' limits) (VA)
Indices and sets	
$t \in T$	Set of time intervals
$J \in J$	Horizon: if 1, variable is within optimization horizon, if 2, variable is part of the next horizon
$s \in S$	Segment of inverter's linearization curve; $\in \{1 - line\ segment, 2 - constant\ segment\}$

This model is formulated with one objective function:

Cost Minimization Objective (OF1): This function aims to minimize the total cost of energy supply, incorporating market energy prices, the degradation costs of ESS technologies (factored by weight $k1$), and the operational timeframe. Mathematically, it is expressed as the summation of product terms involving the absolute power dispatched, market price, and degradation costs over the considered time horizon (Equation 16).

Objective function:

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} (P_t^{abs} \hat{\lambda}_t^{market} + k1 * eDeg) \Delta t \quad (16)$$

Below are the constraints for the optimization algorithm, including:

Power Balance: Ensuring the total power absorbed by the system equals the net of power injected, withdrawn, and consumed by the load.

Maximum Power Limits: Imposing ceilings on the power that can be exchanged with the grid and the power that can be charged/discharged by the ESS.

Energy Content Updating: Dictating the evolution of the energy content in the ESS from one-time step to the next, constrained by the system's capacity limits.

Degradation Estimation: Accounting for the degradation of the ESS based on discharge activities, linearized to simplify the model while retaining accuracy (Equations 18 to 27).

Constraints:

$$P_t^{abs} = P_t^+ - P_t^- + \hat{P}_t^{load}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (18)$$

$$P_t^{abs} \leq \overline{PCC}^{limit} \delta_t^{PCC}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (19)$$

$$P_t^+ \leq \overline{PAC,+} \delta_t^{BESS}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (20)$$

$$P_t^- \leq \overline{PAC,-} (1 - \delta_t^{BESS}), \quad \forall t \in T \quad (21)$$

$$P_t^+ \hat{\eta}^+ \leq \overline{PDC,+}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{P_t^-}{\hat{\eta}^-} \leq \overline{PDC,-}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (23)$$

$$E_{t=1} = \hat{E}^{ini} + \left(P_{t=1}^+ \hat{\eta}^+ - \frac{P_{t=1}^-}{\hat{\eta}^-} \right) \Delta t \quad (24)$$

$$E_t = E_{t-1} + \left(P_t^+ \hat{\eta}^+ - \frac{P_t^-}{\hat{\eta}^-} \right) \Delta t, \quad \forall t \in]1, T] \quad (25)$$

$$\underline{E} \leq E_t \leq \overline{E}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (26)$$

$$E_t^{deg} = \hat{m}^{deg} \times \frac{P_t^-}{\hat{\eta}^-} \Delta t, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (27)$$

The constraints applied in the general formulation include: (18), an equilibrium equation, where the power absorbed by the system is equal to the difference between the injected power and withdrawn power; (19) to limit, when applicable, a maximum power limit at the connection to the grid ; (20) and (21) not to allow for the charge and discharge of the BESS at the same time; (24) and (25) to update the energy content of the BESS between steps (\hat{E}^{ini} is the BESS initial energy content); and (26) to bound that energy content within the battery's

limits. For the degradation, referred to next, the capacity loss curve is linearized by the least squares' approximation, forcing it to intersect the origin. The line's slope \hat{m}^{deg} is used to estimate the degradation caused by each discharge cycle using (27).

2.3.2 Signal Dispatch Identification

In the First optimization model:

The output of this first optimization model is based on the first proposed optimization model. The code prints the status of the optimization problem (e.g., whether it's feasible and solved). It prints the optimal solution, which includes power input, power output, and State of Energy (SOE) for each hour of the day. The code also plots various graphs to visualize the load profile, power input, power output, SOE, and the difference between power input and output. It also provides the result of the total energy charged into the battery as an absolute value and percentage of the total load energy demand. Table 4 shows the optimal input-demand dispatch solution (Figure 21).

Table 4. Optimal solution of dispatch.

Hour (h)	Power Input kW (P_{in})	Power Output kW (P_{out})	SOE (kWh)
0	0.0	0.0	0.0
1	250.0	0.0	250.0
2	0.0	32.0	218.0
3	0.0	31.0	187.0
4	0.0	31.0	156.0
5	0.0	31.0	125.0
6	125.0	0.0	250.0
7	0.0	57.0	193.0
8	0.0	76.0	117.0
9	0.0	117.0	0.0
10	250.0	0.0	250.0
11	0.0	155.0	95.0
12	0.0	95.0	0.0
13	198.0	0.0	198.0
14	0.0	90.0	108.0
15	0.0	108.0	0.0
16	233.0	0.0	233.0
17	0.0	88.0	145.0
18	0.0	78.0	67.0
19	0.0	67.0	0.0
20	106.0	0.0	106.0
21	0.0	39.0	67.0
22	0.0	34.0	33.0
23	0.0	33.0	0.0

The SOE values reflect the absolute energy content in the battery at different hours, measured in kWh, as implemented by the optimization model. This optimization approach of

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

this study allows the SOE to reflect the actual kWh stored in the battery at any time. Moreover, in this simulation, the total Energy Provided to the Load by the battery is 1162.0 kWh by the battery, while the total energy demanded $E_{Total\ Demand}$ The load uses 1698.0 kWh of energy. The battery supplies 68.43% of the energy if the initial energy capacity is maintained.

The model's output provides an hourly schedule of the battery and the percentage of energy consumed by the load supplied by the battery. Figure 22, Figure 23 and Figure 24 provide examples of load, battery dispatch, and SOE.

Figure 22. Recurring load as input.

Figure 23. Optimal dispatch of the battery.

In Figure 23, six charging moments can be identified. Two of which achieve the maximum power. Reducing the number of charging moments would prevent the battery from being unavailable to provide energy to the load. However, this could only be done by increasing the battery's energy capacity. It does, however, given the inputs provided, maximize the energy it is capable of providing. In Figure 24, one can observe the initial and final SOE at the beginning of each hour to be the same, which was set to zero in the example provided, but it can be adjusted to 20%, 50% or any other value the user may desire.

Figure 24. Battery SOE at the beginning of each hour during the cycle.

This exercise, however, is not enough to ensure the maximum energy supplied to the load by the battery is attained since it depends on the energy capacity considered as an input (considered initially to be 250 kWh, following a C-rate of 1). For this reason, a “for loop” is run with the same script but varying the energy capacity from $E_{Min} = 125$ kWh to $E_{Max} = 1700$ kWh in steps of 100 kWh. This results in different values of percentages of energy demand supplied by the battery, which can be seen in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Elbow method for battery capacity identification.

Similar to the elbow method used in heuristics, the same approach can be applied to the present dimensioning exercise of the energy capacity to find the ideal number of clusters in unsupervised learning approaches. In this case, using the “elbow” or “knee of a curve” as a cutoff point means graphically choosing the point where diminishing returns are no longer worth the additional cost. This means that the more the battery’s energy capacity is increased, the lower the ratio of returns of the % increase of supplied energy by the battery is achieved. This happens because the battery needs to be charged at certain moments throughout the day. When it does, it cannot charge at the same time. Hence, a choice must be made between the time it spends charging (not supplying energy to the load) and the energy it can store. In this example, the area of choice could range from 250 kWh to 500 kWh). The 500-kWh value is chosen for the remaining model explanation, allowing the battery to satisfy 75% of the load demand. Note that a new battery dispatch must be obtained after choosing a new energy capacity value. This means that the optimization step has to be run once more to obtain a new version of Table 4.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

In summary, this methodology step alone optimizes how a battery should charge and discharge over a day to maximize the energy it provides to meet a given load profile while adhering to the battery's capacity constraints. It is a valuable tool for energy management and storage systems. The dispatch is the input for the next step of the methodology (Hybridization model).

In the Second optimization model:

Here, the model's output is based on the second proposed optimization model and

Table 5 shows the optimal dispatch solution.

Table 5. Optimal solution of dispatch.

Hour (h)	Power Input kW (P_{in})	Power Output kW (P_{out})	SOE (kWh)
0	0.0	0.0	0.0
1	91.3	0.0	86.8
2	108.0	0.0	189.4
3	109.0	0.0	292.9
4	109.0	0.0	396.5
5	109.0	0.0	500.0
6	0.0	0.0	500.0
7	0.0	0.0	500.0
8	0.0	0.0	500.0
9	0.0	0.0	500.0
10	0.0	31.0	467.4
11	0.0	15.0	451.6
12	0.0	0.0	451.6
13	0.0	0.0	451.6
14	0.0	0.0	451.6
15	0.0	0.0	451.6
16	0.0	88.0	358.9
17	0.0	90.0	264.2
18	0.0	78.0	182.1
19	0.0	67.0	111.6
20	0.0	48.0	61.1
21	0.0	39.0	20.0
22	0.0	0.0	20.0
23	0.0	19.0	0.0

2.4 Battery Hybridization Model

Figure 26 illustrates a detailed flowchart of step 3 that implemented hybridization model.

Figure 26. A detailed flowchart of the hybridization model is shown in step 3.

2.4.1 Cut-off Principles

Building upon previous work from [6], we have followed the same mathematical approach, tackled some of its shortcomings, and applied it to diverse needs. Instead, we focused on developing a pipeline to output HESS sizing solutions based on a load profile input, real data, and real output options. The following steps were taken:

- First, an Excel version was developed, which helped to declare mathematically the hybridisation model.
- Second, once all the details were fine-tuned, we converted the code to Python using the mathematical dependences learned from the development in the Excel tool and integrated it with the initial two steps of the model.
- Third, we validated the outputs of our Python tool with those from the literature [6] and the Excel tool using simple generic input signals.

As stated earlier, one of the main reasons for converting the code to Python was to have the tool run in an open-source format; however, this was not the only reason. The Python implementation provided some freedom to use different libraries and enabled seamless replication. Our model does not require the SOC to be zero at the beginning and the end of the daily cycle. It does, however, require it to be the same. The model does not foresee that the batteries exchange energy between each other. Even though it could increase the

hybridization area of solutions, we found that it is not efficient at all to exchange energy between batteries due to their intrinsic efficiency.

As described in Figure 16, the battery hybridization model is the 3rd step of the present work, so it depends on the outputs of the previous blocks to have a functioning input. So, as we can see, the BES hybridization model receives a battery dispatch signal as input, presenting a hybridization area of viable solutions as output. As we will explain in further detail, the hybridization area of viable solutions is an area between two plotted curves, allowing us to determine if presented solutions of BES pairing are viable. The dispatch signal, generated by the processed data in the previous blocks, provides a 24-hour dispatch signal with a time-step of 1h. This dispatch signal consists of a two-column array with a time column in hours [h] and a power column in kilo Watts [kW], as presented in Table 4.

The model calculates the hybridization curve by splitting the original arrays into four arrays, two of which correspond to the base signal and two to the peak signal. This is done multiple times for different cutoff values (split percentages), and each one will generate a point that will make up the hybridization curve. Figure 27 shows the procedure regarding the cut-offs and provides an example for a generic signal for simplicity of presentation. In Figure 27 (a), an example of a generic signal is presented and a cut-offline of 50% is shown. Cutting the signal at 50% creates the base and peak areas to be allocated to both batteries with the corresponding Power and Energy identified. The same procedure is repeated for different cut-offs creating the grey dashed line in Figure 27 (b), with each dot corresponding to the cut-offs from 0-100%, and the resulting power and energy values.

Figure 27. (a) Signal cut-off example of 50%; (b) and Hybridization curve example.

So, to calculate all the cut-of points demonstrated in the previous Figure 27 (b) we apply the following Equations [28-29]:

$$\text{Power Capacity (y axis)} \rightarrow \max(\text{Original Signal} \times \text{CutOff}) = \max(5 \times 0.5) = 2.5\text{kW} \quad (28)$$

The y-axis coordinate is given by the maximum value of the power cut-off signal. The reader can see that by applying the cut-off at 50%, the maximum value of the base power signal would be 2.5 kW. Now, we take this signal, calculate the corresponding base energy signal, and then apply the same logic. This can be seen in the following equation.

$$\text{Energy Capacity(x axis)} \rightarrow \max\left(\int_0^{24} \text{Power}_{\text{Cutoff}}(t) dt\right) = 21 \text{ kWh} \quad (29)$$

Power Cut Off is the power signal for a specific cut-off value.

So, for the cut-off of 50% we get the point [21, 2.5] for the base signal, the same can be done for the peak signal which would give us the coordinates [9, 2.5] which complements the original signal that had 30 kWh of maximum energy and 5 kW of maximum power, this is the same as the 100% cut off. This must be done for every cut-off value, and each cut-of value will generate new base and peak signals for both power and energy. Finally, the smaller the increment the more precise the hybridization curve.

2.4.2 Hybridization Curve

Applying the same rationale to the input signal in Table 4, but now with the new capacity considered, 500 kWh, the updated components of the dispatch signal, power, and energy, can be inserted in the hybridization model. The corresponding hybridization curve obtained for the first optimization dispatch is shown in Figure 28. then in a yellow dotted line. Notice that an inverted second axis was inserted for both Peak and Base batteries to appear. The bottom and left axis refer to the Base battery and the right and upper axis to the Peak battery. The possible optimal configurations must fall inside the area between the hybridization curve and the original signal line. All points where the two battery lines starting from the origin, intersect are possible combinations.

Figure 28. Hybridization curve.

By analyzing the hybridization curve of Figure 28, we can now extract possible pairing solutions for the hybrid BES system or check if a proposed solution is viable. Another metric that can be extracted from the hybridization curve is the hybridization potential, originally defined as H as per Equation 30.

$$H = \frac{(\text{Area below purple vector} - \text{Area below hybridization curve})}{(\text{Area below purple vector})} [\%] \quad (30)$$

The hybridization potential is the normalized area between the original signal (purple linear vector) and the hybridization curve (yellow) dotted line. This area provides all possible optimal solutions for hybrid combinations. Thus, H is equal to 0.0 or 0% if the hybridization curve is equal to the original signal, and it is equal to 1.0 or 100% if the hybridization curve follows the base power x-axis and the peak power y-axis.

In this case, H is equal to 0.13, meaning that hybridization potential is equal to 13%, Analyzing the new dispatch of the 250 kW and 500 kWh and retrieving the maximum values for power and energy reached a single BES system would have to have the following characteristics:

- Ideal Solution (Original signal):
 - Power: 250 kW.
 - Energy: 477 kWh.
 - C-RATE: 0.52 h⁻¹

For analysis, we consider two theoretical solutions, considering each has two batteries, one for peak response (PP, EP) and one for base response (PB, EB), two examples can be seen in Table 6 (one optimal and another not).

Table 6. Example of two proposed BES systems.

	Solution 1	Solution 2
Power Base	80 kW.	200 kW.
Energy Base	110 kWh.	200 kWh.
C _{RATE} Base	0.73 h ⁻¹	1.0 h ⁻¹
Power Peak	170 kW.	50 kW.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Energy Peak	367 kWh.	277 kWh.
C_{RATE} Peak	0.46 h ⁻¹	0.18 h ⁻¹

By plotting the values one can observe, paying special attention to the double referential, solution 1 falls within the hybridization curve and solution 2 does not as shown in [Figure 28](#). Thus, for a solution to be viable, the vectors generated by plotting the values (PP, EP) and (PS, EB) must intersect, meeting, inside the hybridization curve otherwise the system can either be under-dimensioned or over-dimensioned.

On closer analysis and comparison with the original single battery signal, we see that the potential Solution 1 can output 250 kW in terms of power and 477 kWh in terms of energy, just exactly like the single battery, so it is perfectly sized. Similarly, Solution 2, can also output 250 kW power, and 477 kWh in terms of energy, however, as the combination falls outside the hybridization curve, it is not an optimal size solution given their C-rates.

Moreover, the hybridization curve enables the assessment of potential BESS pairings by comparing them against the curve. A proposed BES configuration is considered viable if it falls within the hybridization area, implying that it can effectively meet the load demands while adhering to the system's capacity limitations. Conversely, solutions outside this area are deemed non-optimal, indicating either under-dimensioning or over-dimensioning of the system based on the given C-rates. This mathematical approach, encapsulated in the hybrid curve calculation, is fundamental to the Battery Hybridization Model. It not only facilitates the sizing and pairing of base and peak battery systems based on actual load profiles but also provides a quantitative measure H to evaluate the efficiency and viability of these pairings. The hybridization potential quantifies the normalized area between the original dispatch signal and the hybridization curve, offering insights into the percentage of viable solutions within the total solution space.

Here, to cross-load analysis of the second optimization proposed model, the signal to the Hybridization model is: [0.0, -91.315789, -108.0, -109.0, -109.0, -109.0, 0.0, 0.0, 31.0, 15.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 88.0, 90.0, 78.0, 67.0, 48.0, 39.0, 0.0, 19.0, 0.0]. Figure 29 shows the hybridization curve based on the output from the second battery dispatch optimization model. One can observe that the hybridization area changed significantly, which is actual the result of changing the optimization function. The area may change due to the dispatch but also due to the load considered.

Figure 29. Hybridization curve.

2.5 Commercial solution

This section will present the available commercial solutions based on data from the literature and available BSS in the market.

Regarding technology selection, ESS technologies fall into three main categories: chemical, electrical, and mechanical energy storage, as previously discussed [1,2,4], with their characteristics detailed in Figure 1 and Table 1. Understanding the base and peak power capacities, corresponding energy capacities, and C-rates is crucial for effective technology selection. These parameters are instrumental in guiding the technology choice within the hybridization area and the sizing methodology utilized in HESS.

To clarify, data from Table 1 are visualized in Figure 30, displaying a Ragone plot for technology selection based on power and energy capacity ranges, as reviewed in the literature.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 30. Ragone plot illustrates technology selection by power and energy capacity range, derived from data in Table 1.

It is relevant to mention that the theoretical potential solutions provided in Table 1 may not be found in the market. Based on the range of possibilities given by the Hybridization area of Figure 28. and the details in Table 1, a review of commercial battery solutions has been conducted. Table 7 These lists provide an example of real-life battery configurations. Two Lithium batteries are considered: Battery 1 as a base battery and Battery 2 as the peak battery. Data from the single battery is placed in the table to compare hybrid and non-hybrid batteries.

Table 7. Example of commercial technology in the market.

	Battery 1	Battery 2	Single Battery
Power Base	52 kW.	200 kW.	250 kW.
Energy Base	78 kWh.	400 kWh.	500 kWh
C-base Base	0.67 h ⁻¹	0.50 h ⁻¹	1 h ⁻¹
Technology	Lithium	Lithium	Lithium
Dimensions of the battery	1800* 853* 336 mm	1200*800*2050 mm	3048*2438*2743 mm
Weight	562 kg	1250 kg	6434 kg
Operating Temperature	-30° C to 50° C	-25° C to 45° C	-25° C to 45° C
Voltage range	348V	420V ~ 850V	710V ~ 1250V
Manufacture	Torqueedo	Dawnice	Generic Industrial Power
Datasheet/ Reference	[51]	[52]	[53]

Comparing the hybrid configuration of Batteries 1 and 2 with a single large-scale non-hybrid battery highlights the hybrid system's benefits for ESS applications. The hybrid setup is

significantly lighter, 3.55 times less than the single unit at 6434 kg, and features adaptable dimensions, facilitating easier installation, transportation, and spatial efficiency. Its wider operational temperature range and voltage flexibility also capitalize on each battery technology's unique attributes, improving system reliability and adaptability. Moreover, the hybrid approach reduces the physical deployment size, requiring two smaller locations instead of one large one.

In [Figure 31](#), these batteries are represented within the hybridization curve area, indicating their complementary nature and suitability for the hybridization model's requirements.

Figure 31. Ragone plot illustrates technology selection by power and energy capacity range, derived from data in Table 7.

As illustrated in Figure 30, the batteries are marked as pink and black dots, showcasing the flexibility in choosing technological solutions beyond Lithium, such as NaS, FES, Flow Batteries, or SMEs.

In summary, apart from the size, one should consider the versatility of having a hybrid system instead of one. It will allow for a reduction of the hosting physical location. Hybrid systems can support cases in which there is the need to a) Increase already existing capacity, b) a situation in which we cannot rely on a single battery, c) a situation in which one cannot install another battery in the same location for security reasons, due to other activities taking place that may prevent the installation of certain technologies d) explore the characteristics of different technologies to leverage overall performance (response time, degradation, cost, etc...).

2.6 Model Validation and Performance

In this section, the model is validated against a full optimization approach. It also provides performance indicators for running the model.

With respect to performance and validation, running the total model takes 30.45 seconds to process a full year of data, perform the optimization of dispatch and output the hybridization area. Most of the processing time (24 seconds) is attributed to the DTW block to cluster the data. The validation step was achieved by comparing the results to a full optimization approach for Renewable Energy Communities asset sizing, proposed by [54] hereafter referred to as the “full optimization approach”. The optimization function in below was initially used for different types of asset sizing. The implementation is done in python using the Pulp library and a mixed integer linear programming approach following the stated objective function:

$$\text{Opt_function} = \sum_{n \in \text{set_meters}} \left(\sum_{t \in \text{time_series}} (e_{\text{sup}}[n][t] \cdot l_{\text{buy}}[n][t] - e_{\text{sur}}[n][t] \cdot l_{\text{sell}}[n][t] + e_{\text{slc}}[n][t] \cdot l_{\text{grid}}[t]) + p_{\text{cont}}[n] \cdot l_{\text{cont}}[n] \cdot \text{nr_days} + p_{\text{gn_new}}[n] \cdot l_{\text{gic}}[n] \cdot \text{nr_days} + e_{\text{bn_new}}[n] \cdot l_{\text{bic}}[n] \cdot \text{nr_days} \right) \quad (31)$$

This formula represents the summation over all meters n of the sum of the energy supply, energy surplus, and energy balance multiplied by their respective prices, summed over all time periods t in the time series. Additionally, it includes the cost of contracted power (p_{cont}), the cost of new generated power ($p_{\text{gn_new}}$), and the cost of new battery ($e_{\text{bn_new}}$).

where,

E_{sup} : energy supplied to n from its retailer [kWh]

l_{buy} : supply energy tariff [€/kWh]

e_{sur} : energy surplus sold by n to its retailer [kWh]

l_{sell} : feed in energy tariff [€/kWh]

e_{slc} : energy self-consumed by n [kWh]

l_{grid} : access tariff of the local grid [€/kWh]

p_{cont} : contracted power tariff by n [kW]

l_{cont} : contracted power tariff, adjusted to one day [€/kW.day]

Nr_days : number of days in the optimization horizon [days]

$p_{\text{gn_new}}$: new installed RES capacity at n [kW]

l_{gic} : investment cost for RES installation, adjusted to one day [€/kW.day]

$e_{\text{bn_new}}$: new installed storage system(s) capacity at n [kWh]

l_{bic} : investment cost for storage installation, adjusted to one day [€/kWh.day]

n : meter number

t : each of the time steps defined in the time window analysis

The following steps were performed for the validation:

1. The clustering load diagram from Step 1 was the load input to the optimization function.
2. The model was run, and the total battery capacity and the time taken to run were recorded.
3. The input of the first battery's capacity of the HESS example in [Table 6](#) (110 kWh), the initial installed capacity was provided to get the recommended second battery capacity. The inserted C-rate was the corresponding 0.73, and the resulting capacity was compared to the one provided in the example shown in [Table 6](#).

The result for the energy capacity sizing from the full optimization approach model was 523.28 kWh, considering a battery efficiency of 90%, which is aligned with the example of the proposed model in this study (500 kWh) for the considered load diagram. When given an initial capacity of 110 kWh already installed, the model proposed a new installation of 353.88 kWh when a C-Rate of 0.73 was provided. This value compares to the 367.00 kWh provided by our model in Table 4, which is acceptable for validating the results. It should be said, however, that the comparing model does not allow for a match with commercial solutions, such as the solution proposed in this study, and does not achieve the hybrid combinations by adjusting the C-Rates, resulting in an energy-based and power-based battery combination, as they are inputs to the optimization of the full optimization approach model and not outputs, as they are in our approach.

In terms of processing time, compared to the full optimization approach model, it outperforms it for large data sets, as presented in the example provided, for which the full optimization model may take several hours, depending on the optimizer used. However, if only 24 h datasets or smaller are considered, the full optimization approach is faster (around 1 sec) compared to the proposed model in this study (6.45 seconds). Another metric used in our model is the quantitative H indicator, which provides an optimal area of solutions, allowing for an alignment with commercial solutions. In contrast, other studies tend to neglect this practical linkage.

2.7 Benefits of the Methodology for InterSTORE

This study recognizes the opportunity to develop a practical HESS sizing tool with an integrated pipeline and presents the developments and verification results from such a proposed model. The model's modular design, where each phase operates independently, enhances flexibility, allowing for easy adjustments and updates to specific parts without impacting the entire model. This approach simplifies error isolation and troubleshooting and promotes scalability and reusability of components in different contexts.

All requirements for the model development were fulfilled. Verifying the model using data from UC05 clarified the procedure. Even though viable solutions can mathematically be identified from the model output, they may not exist as a commercial solution. This strengthens the requirement for an optimal area of solutions instead of a single option.

The hybrid storage sizing model shows the superiority of the hybrid system in terms of versatility, size and adaptability to physical constraints, making it a more favourable option compared to traditional single-battery systems when there is a need for:

1. capacity increase,
2. the case where one cannot rely on a single battery,
3. the case in which a given technology cannot be deployed in the same location as an already existing battery.
4. complementarity of characteristic and performances.

2.7.1 Python Open-Source Implementation

The proposed model's structure encompasses three distinct components: identifying recurring patterns, developing an optimization model, and formulating a hybridization curve. Access to the script for these components is provided on GitHub [55].

3 Multiservice Approach for HESS System

This section delves into the fundamental role of HESS with an optimal multi-service approach from HESStec point of view in addressing the pressing challenges of renewable integration and unlocking the vast potential of multi-service operations in future power grids. HESS represents a ground-breaking approach that transcends the constraints of conventional storage systems by integrating multiple storage technologies, such as batteries and ultra-capacitors, to achieve a synergistic balance between power and energy capabilities. By leveraging the complementary characteristics of these diverse storage elements, HESS emerges as a transformative solution poised to revolutionize energy storage paradigms.

In contrast to the single-service focus of traditional BESS, the proposed multi service with HESS offers a holistic and adaptable framework that can cater to a wide spectrum of services with varying natures, encompassing both high-power and high-energy requirements. This versatility not only enhances grid stability, but also facilitates the seamless integration of renewable energy sources, driving the transition towards a cleaner and more sustainable energy ecosystem.

Furthermore, the operational flexibility afforded by HESS, enables operators to navigate the complexities of modern energy markets with agility and efficiency. By dynamically allocating resources based on real-time demand and grid conditions, HESS maximizes the value proposition of energy storage investments, unlocking new revenue streams and optimizing asset utilization. As the energy landscape continues to evolve, the integration of HESS promises to drive innovation, foster resilience, and pave the way towards a more sustainable and inclusive energy future.

Through a comprehensive analysis, this section aims to elucidate how HESS empowers operators to capitalize on emerging opportunities in energy markets, while ensuring resilience and reliability in the face of evolving grid dynamics.

3.1 The Challenges of High-RES Integration

Technological advances, such as the use of modern power electronic systems with different ESS, as well as the large-scale penetration of renewable energy sources, have led to a reformulation of the conventional power systems, moving toward a more flexible scheme. The demand for electricity is increasing phenomenally because of technological complexity and innovations. Moreover, the incorporation of more and more non-synchronous generator, as renewable energy sources (RES), in addition to low inertia issues and the reduction of fossil fuel generation that provides most of the flexibility and ancillary services in today's system, will further aggravate the grid quality and stability. The power production of RES, which utilise primary energy sources that are free but have a variable nature, must be balanced in order to maintain the frequency equilibrium, including forecast output deviations. This poses a significant challenge for technology providers and system operators, as they are not only tasked with advancing their technological capabilities but also expected to adapt to modifications in grid codes.

In the next figures, a study of (Ten-Year Network Development Plans) TYNDP 2022 from ENTSO-E, is discussed, showing the ratio between the sum of wind and solar photovoltaic generation (not considering all other RES) and total generation. The authors include three different scenarios: Distributed Energy (DE), Global Ambition (GA) and National Trends (NT) at two timeframes: 2030 and 2040. The meaning of each scenario is explained as follows:

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

- National Trends (NT) is based on TSOs data up to 2040 translating national policies and strategies as stated end of 2020 and focusing on the sole electricity, methane and hydrogen energy carriers.
- Distributed Energy (DE) is driven by a willingness of the society to achieve energy autonomy. This translates into a strong decentralised drive towards decarbonisation which implies a maximization of renewable energy production and a strong decrease of energy imports. It is based on a holistic view of the European energy system up to 2050.
- Global Ambition (GA) emphasizes a transition driven by a global move towards the 2015 Paris Agreement targets. This implies the development of a wide range of renewable and low-carbon technologies (many being centralised) and the use of global energy trade as a tool to accelerate decarbonization. It is also based on a holistic view of the European energy system up to 2050.

Figure 32. Wind+PV vs total generation (ENTSO-E, 2023) [38].

It can be observed that high ratios of RES generation will be achieved, above 80% for some scenarios. This means that reduced amount of controllable generating units lead to high flexibility needs in normal operation. This may lead to a weaker system with lower inertia. As a consequence, the services such as frequency control will be more challenging.

Frequency variations occur in power systems due to mismatches between active power generation and demand. It is well known that the energy store in the rotating mass of synchronous generator have an immediate inertial response that helps to maintain the system frequency in secure values. However, from 2030 to the 2040 scenarios inertia in all synchronous areas will decrease, even in Continental Europe. In TYNDP 2022 has been studied the inertia decrease and, in Continental Europe for example, the average inertia through 2040 is lower and the minimum is around 0.5 s.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 33. Inertia constant (ENTSO-E, 2023) [38].

With very low inertia, the system becomes more vulnerable to experience high frequency excursions and even blackout. Furthermore, in instances where there is an imbalance between demand and generation, the grid frequency may deviate from its rated value. In such cases, the regulation control system of generators connected to the grid will automatically adjust the active power output, either increasing (to counteract frequency drop) or decreasing (to counteract frequency increase). This adjustment is aimed at mitigating the variation characteristics of the grid frequency. According to Red Eléctrica España (REE) [7], a substantial worsening of frequency stability conditions on the Iberian Peninsula, which are significantly worse than those in the central subsystems of continental Europe. Steady-state frequencies < 49.8 Hz more frequent in future scenarios (up to 50% of the time). There is evidence of a greater need for primary regulation reserve, with renewables, energy storage and electronic device capabilities supplying this service.

Figure 34. Frequency (Hz) in steady-state vs time (%) (REE, 2020) [37].

The REE Grid Code specifies that non-synchronous plants have to act when the frequency deviates ± 10 mHz from the reference value, while the activation threshold for LFSM-U and LFSM-O is ± 200 mHz. However, for the UK grid code the insensibility value is ± 15 mHz, 50.4 Hz for LFSM-O and 49.5 Hz for LFSM-U.

The available inertia and the mismatch between generation and demand are the two factors that influence the initial rate of change of frequency (RoCoF). It is foreseeable that RoCoF and imbalance will increase, more in areas with high penetration of RES. It is important to note that the loss of generation necessary to trigger a certain level of RoCoF is higher in large synchronous areas than in smaller ones. For example, in certain hours, a 100 MW power imbalance in Ireland (Ireland and Northern-Ireland) would already be sufficient to

trigger the same RoCoF as a 16 GW power imbalance in Continental Europe. The system operation limit is currently specified as 1 Hz/s in Europe by ENTSO-E (ENTSO-E, 2023).

Figure 35. Imbalance leading to 1 Hz/s RoCoF (ENTSO-E, 2023) [38].

For REE, the admissibility criteria in Spain is a RoCoF < 1 Hz/s, except in La Palma, where is < 2 Hz/s. In the UK Grid Code, an active RoCoF response power control is defined to inject or absorb active power when the frequency change more than 1 Hz/s. The Figure 36 shows a comparison between the maximum RoCoF in the Iberian Peninsula and Center Europe.

Figure 36. Iberian Peninsula vs Europe max. RoCoF (Hz/s) vs time (%) (REE, 2020) [37].

Another important issue in low inertia scenario is system split events that can lead large-scale blackouts, larger, longer and quicker frequency disturbances. Some studies that are presented in TYNDY 2022 shows that many cases of RoCoF exceeding 1 Hz/s for each subsystem of CE synchronous Area.

Some solutions have been proposed to contribute to securing power system performance against frequency-related disturbances. An immediate inertial response can only be met by synchronous generators. In the future new capabilities, such as Grid-forming Converters with HESS with high power storage technologies will be necessary as well as the use of GFM for HVDC interconnection between areas in order to mitigate the system split problem.

Furthermore, other consequence of the synchronous generation reduction in the network is the decrease of voltage stability. The short-circuit power is a well-known key performance

indication (KPI) which serves as an indication of the grid strength. As converter-connected RES replaces synchronous generation and the generated power has to be transmitted over long distances between generation units and demand centres, the short-circuit power will tend to fall to a lower level. This can result in voltage dip. Once more, this problem could be mitigated with the incorporation of GFM capabilities and must be well distributed to handle the various possible situations and faults. According to REE, the power generator module should support voltage dips, contribute to active power restoration and inject fault current in case of faults. The UK Grid Code also specifies that the Power Park module should remain transiently stable and connected to the system without tripping, and that it should restore active power output according to a defined profile of voltage dip.

Based on the information presented in this section, it becomes apparent that in future power grids characterized by a high proportion of renewable energy sources, the significance of energy storage and advanced technologies in facilitating a multitude of services becomes increasingly pronounced. The adoption of an advanced multi-service approach, encapsulated within the framework of hybrid energy storage solutions, emerges as a pivotal objective for companies like HESStec to effectively address these challenges. It can help to cover wider ranges of services for providing to the grid.

3.2 Grid Services

After witnessing a complete paradigm shift in current power systems, characterized by significant structural and operational changes, it becomes evident that addressing the technical challenges inherent in this new paradigm is crucial. Therefore, it is essential to underscore the necessity of equipping the power system with what are commonly referred to as grid services or functionalities. In essence, the primary objectives of these grid services or functionalities can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Improve the quality, supply and efficiency of electrical energy, ensuring the stability of the network.
- 2) In reference to the high penetration of renewable energies, it is necessary to increase the degree of their manageability, since they are stochastic in nature (for example, solar and wind energy).
- 3) Furthermore, there is a need to provide certain electricity generation plants, such as solar or wind generation plants, with certain grid functionalities to improve the economic profitability of such as power plants. Due to the high penetration of renewable energy that occurs in future scenarios, the price of energy in the wholesale market will decrease considerably, even reaching zero or negative prices at certain hours of the day (for example, in the central hours of the day, where the peak of PV generation occurs), which produces a loss of economic profitability of those non-manageable electricity generation plants, such as solar and wind plants. For this reason and thanks to certain types of grid services or functionalities, it is possible to increase their economic profitability, thanks mainly to optimal participation in the different electricity markets, such as the daily market, secondary regulation market (aFRR), intraday markets, etc.

In general, the definition of a grid service depends on 1) the needs of the grid and 2) the features of the available technologies. It is complicated to define a general but precise classification of grid services, as they depend on the specific market and regulations in every

specific location. The definition of these regulations and the market mechanisms are established as a function of the needs of the power system of every country (depending on the radial/meshed structure, renewable penetration, consumption profile, etc.).

The needs of the European backbone are different than UK's power system, or different than the one in North American grid. As an example, frequency regulation is defined in a different way depending on the specific market: PJM, Nacional Grid UK or Spain. Besides the technical conditions, there are other factors, such as political ones, that highly impact the energy strategy of each country.

The definition of grid services is also influenced by the features of the available technologies. This fact can be also illustrated by frequency regulation services. In many of them, independently of the frequency response to be provided, the regulations require a minimum of a 15-minute backup. The fast-transient response of the frequency regulation service should not be related to a 15 minutes backup. This restriction is related to the features of power batteries (such as LTO) and it limits the use of other high-power technologies, such as ultracapacitors, that may offer a more competitive solution under other rules based on their particular features.

From the grid point of view, power and energy issues should be identified and decoupled as their origins and objectives are well differentiated. The [Figure 37](#) depicts different various grid services over the frame of a Ragone plot. There is high difference between power and energy issues and they should be separately solved. The solution for the power and energy issues is optimally provided by different types of technology with different specific energy (Wh/kg) and specific power (W/kg).

Grid services can be parametrized as a function of:

- Duration: from seconds (high power services) to hours (high energy services), with a broad variety of intermediate possibilities.
- Shape: services does not exhibit a rectangular constant full power operation profile.

This is a very important issue specially in the case of power services. For instance:

- Frequency regulation in certain markets may have a triangular shape profile. Other profiles like POD have a sinusoidal shape.
- The start-up of a diesel generator will have different stages, from an initial full response during the synchronization period to a power ramp until generator reaches full power.
- Renewable integration will require a ramp rate response related to the transient change on the availability of the response.
- Symmetry: this is a particular feature of the service. Some services require a symmetry response by the technology. This is very important, for example in case of batteries since this affects the choice of the technology as most battery technologies have a different charge/discharge power ratio.
- Frequency: a short duration service with a high repeatability will impact at the service life of the technology and will require a rest time on certain technologies such as battery energy storage.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 37. Grid services represented over the frame of a Ragone Plot.

At this point, it is observed that current and future power systems will require certain assets to provide a multitude of services to the system, whether to improve the stability of the network, the quality, supply and efficiency of electrical energy or other factors such as increasing the degree of manageability of renewable generation sources or increasing the economic profitability of electricity generation plants, as described above. For such scenario the use of hybrid solution with multi service functionality is of interest.

We would like to highlight that the integration of power and energy-based services within a storage expansion model markedly influences the ultimate recommendations for storage investments. Put simply, our aim is to identify the most advantageous mixture of ESS that serves a variety of service requirements.

BESS are widely adopted for their high energy density, enabling them to store large amounts of energy for extended durations. BESS excels in applications requiring long-term energy storage, such as peak shaving and renewable energy time-shifting. Moreover, BESS typically exhibit relatively low self-discharge rates and can be deployed in various configurations to meet specific power and energy demands. Despite their advantages, BESS face certain limitations, particularly in applications requiring high-power. Rapid charging and discharging can induce thermal stresses, leading to efficiency losses and reduced battery lifespan. Additionally, BESS may struggle to provide instantaneous power for applications with dynamic load profiles, necessitating supplementary power conditioning equipment.

In our approach to use multi-service functionality, a hybrid solution is proposed. HESS offers a compelling solution to overcome the limitations of BESS by integrating multiple storage technologies. By combining the strengths of different storage elements, such as batteries and ultra-capacitors, HESS achieves a synergistic balance between power and energy capabilities. As shown in Figure 38, this hybridization is mixing of different source of energy storage technologies for providing a wide range of solutions, from power-based storage components (suitable for high power applications) to energy based storage (energy intensive services) system enables HESS to deliver enhanced performance across a broader spectrum of applications, making it well-suited for multi-service optimization within the energy market.

Figure 38. Hybrid concept, avoiding oversizing depicted over a Ragone diagram.

Some of the main advantages of using HESS over BESS can be as follows:

- **Enhanced Power Range:** The integration of ultra-capacitors with batteries in HESS enables rapid power delivery, making it suitable for applications requiring high-power bursts or fast response times. This capability enhances grid stability, supports frequency regulation, and facilitates seamless integration of renewable energy sources.
- **Improved Energy Management:** HESS optimizes energy management by dynamically allocating power and energy resources based on real-time demand and grid conditions. The combination of high-energy and high-power storage elements allows HESS to address both short-term power fluctuations and long-term energy requirements, ensuring reliable and efficient operation across diverse applications.
- **Increased Operational Flexibility:** HESS offers greater operational flexibility compared to standalone BESS by providing a wider range of services. Whether it's grid ancillary services, peak shaving, or electric vehicle charging, HESS can adapt to varying demands and prioritize different performance metrics as needed, maximizing overall system efficiency and revenue potential.
- **Market Adaptability:** HESS's versatility makes it highly adaptable to market demands. Its ability to provide a diverse range of services enables operators to capitalize on emerging opportunities in energy markets. Whether it's participating in frequency regulation markets, providing grid support services, or optimizing renewable energy integration, HESS offers a competitive edge by offering a flexible and comprehensive solution.

In general, HESS represents a significant advancement in energy storage technology, offering distinct advantages over traditional BESS. By combining the complementary characteristics of different storage technologies, HESS achieves optimal multi-service functionality within the energy market while ensuring market adaptability. Moving forward, further research and development in HESS will continue to drive innovation and accelerate the transition towards a more sustainable and resilient energy infrastructure.

3.3 Proposed Multiservice Methodology

The following diagram (Figure 39) shows how multiservice is implemented in HESStec in a BESS or HESS system. Firstly, with software located in the cloud, all the elements that make up the system are virtualized (batteries, power converters, lines, grid connection, etc.) with the aim of determining the optimal participation of the BESS or HESS in the markets of electrical energy. These markets are mainly three:

1. Daily market.
2. Secondary regulation market (aFRR).
3. Intraday/continuous market.

Once the optimal operation has been determined in the different electrical markets, under a certain optimization window and refresh rate, such as command is sent to the physical layer of the system, located in the field (EMS layer called InMS[®] uGrid). This setpoint is the reference SOC, and the hourly or fifteen-minute periods in which charging or discharging is enabled (α^{ch} and α^{dis} respectively). The objective of the InMS[®] uGrid physical control layer is to follow the reference instructions sent from the cloud (Grid Core), but always complying with the grid code that applies in each case and implementing all those functionalities that may appear as needs of the power system (POD, frequency regulation, voltage regulation, ramp control, etc.). Finally, after calculating in the InMS[®] uGrid the real active and reactive power setpoints for each instant of time that meet the needs identified in the control layer located in the cloud and those identified in the physical control layer in real time InMS uGrid, the hybridization algorithm is responsible for optimally controlling the response of each storage system of different technologies (HESS) to provide an optimal response to such as active and reactive power requirements, minimizing the degradation of the assets that make up the HESS.

In addition, the physical EMS layer (InMS uGrid[®]) has direct analog measurement of the POI (frequency, voltage and current) to be able to implement all grid services and functionalities. Since this measure is very fast, it is possible to implement regulation services that require an almost instantaneous response. Finally, the control layer located in the cloud has real-time information on the state of the system (batteries, renewable resource, etc.) and measurements at the POI. Thanks to this, it is possible to solve the different optimization problems with feedback on the real state of the system, in order to always ensure optimal operation under the current state of the system.

Figure 39. HESStec multiservice basic diagram.

In the following lines the system model equations of the optimization problem (which is executed in the Grid core cloud layer) are described in a generic and summarized way:

$$\max \sum_{t=1}^T [E_t^{DA} c_t^{DA} + P_t^{aFRR} c_t^{aFRR} + P_t^{RR} c_t^{RR} - \sum_{i=1}^N (P_{i,t}^{BESS} c_{i,t}^{BESS})] \quad (32)$$

With constrains of:

- 1) Power system model equations (equality equations).
- 2) Power system operation restrictions (equality and inequality equations).
- 3) Battery/batteries degradation model.
- 4) Market rules (equality and inequality equations).

Where:

- P_t^{aFRR} and P_t^{RR} are the secondary frequency regulation (aFRR) and renewable resource (RR) power at the period 't'.
- E_t^{DA} is the energy injected or absorbed in the day ahead market (DA) at the period 't'.
- $P_{i,t}^{BESS}$ is the power of each 'i' storage system technology at the period time 't'.
- c_t^{DA} , c_t^{aFRR} and c_t^{RR} are the day ahead (DA), secondary frequency regulation (aFRR) and renewable resource (RR) income/cost in the period 't'.
- $c_{i,t}^{BESS}$ is the operating cost of each 'i' storage system technology at the period time 't'.

3.4 Example of Multiservice Assessment in Different Scenarios: HESStec Approach

In this section, for presenting and assessing the performance of the proposed approach, some selected multiservice examples from a project executed in the field is presented and discussed.

3.4.1 Test Scenario1: HESS with Wind Power

The generic diagram of the studied system is presented in Figure 40. As shown in this figure, the system consists of a 3 MW wind power plant with a HESS solution (ultracapacitors and power battery) both connected to an external grid. Rating of UCAP and batteries are 300 kW (@0.56 kV) and 1 MW (@0.47kV), respectively. The rest of the system data are presented in Table 8 and Table 9.

Figure 40. Use case for multiservice example 1.

The following tables show a brief description about the technical specifications of each element at this use case:

Table 8. Technical parameters of studied benchmark (I).

External grid equivalent	Local load	Wind plant profile (A1.2)	Transformer (Tg)	Cable (Lg)
Rating: 58 MVA Inertia: 3,5 s at 20 kV	13,5 MW 12 kV	3 MW as nominal power 12 kV	Rating: 100 MVA 20/12 kV	Length: 0,5 km R=0,125 ohm/km, X=0,106 ohm/km C=0,306 μF/km

Table 9. Technical parameters from HESS system (II).

Transformer T1	Battery parameters
Rating: 1,75 MVA at 0,47/12 kV	1 MW on discharge, 750 kW on charge. Nominal voltage: 963,9 V. Nominal discharge current: 0,13 kA Rated Capacity: 0,407 kAh (393 kWh), Nominal capacity: 0,368 kAh (354,7 kWh)
Transformer T2	UCAP parameters
Rating: 300 kVA at 0,56/12 kV	Rating of 290 kW, Maximum voltage: 720 V and Minimum voltage: 360 V Equivalent ESR: 0,03 ohm, total capacity: 25 Farad

At this first example, it is shown a multiservice operation by implementing two operation modes at the use case described before:

- *Wind following mode with ramp rate:*

This operation mode is characterized by following the maximum available production power, that is, following the wind power profile. The grid services that are implemented in this operating mode are ramp rate and power smoothing, since when the park is connected or disconnected, the power ramp is limited to a certain maximum value (% P_n / min) and in the event of sudden variations in power, this ramp must also be limited. In addition, when faced with weak grids or when required by the TSO, the peak shaving (PS) service is also applied, in order to obtain an active power profile that does not have significant variations that could have a negative impact in the operation or reliability of the system.

Finally, the reference active power of the HESS is calculated as the active power injected into the grid at time 't' (that is the result of the algorithm in previous section), minus the real power produced by the wind farm or wind turbine at that same time. Where:

- P_{real} (t): real wind power profile.
- P_{grid} (t): power profile with ramp rate limitation.
- P_{grid_F} (t): power profile with ramp rate limitation and power smoothing.
- P^{HESS}_{ref} (t): reference power for HESS.

- *Set-point following mode:*

This operation mode consists of following the active power set-point established by the plant operator or TSO. For this, the ramp restrictions must be fulfilled when following the setpoints or connection and disconnection of the plant (ramp rate grid service), in addition to ensuring that the power injected into the grid is that established as a reference in the setpoint (grid service Firming). From the set-point reference power and the power injected into the grid, the reference power of the HESS is calculated to meet the requirements required in this operation mode. Where:

- P_{real} (t): real wind power profile.
- P_{grid} (t): power profile with ramp rate limitation.
- P_{set} (t): set-point power reference.
- P^{HESS}_{ref} (t): reference power for HESS.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 41. Example 1: multiservice test, POI measured signal assessment.

Figure 42. Example 1: multiservice test, POI signal: Power battery assessment.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 43. Example 1: multiservice test, UCAP assessment.

As shown in Figure 41, the functionalities of two services, ramp rate limit and wind power smoothing, are tests in two different modes of wind following with ramp rate and set point following modes. As shown in these figures, first the wind following mode is activated by operator (from 0 to 60 sec) and then from 60 to 145 sec the setpoint following mode is activated. The upper plot confirms the acceptable performance of the control which shows it can follow the wind power profile within a ramp limit with smoother response while it follows the setpoint when setpoint following mode is activated. The next two figures show the power battery (Figure 42) and ultracapacitor (Figure 43) power and energy profile evolution. The smoother response of the system is reached thanks to the contribution from HESS system especially high-power storage, UCAP. As it shows in the following figure, for some periods the output power of storage elements reaches their limit.

Another example in the same use case described above is shown in the next two figures. In this case, the HESS system is providing voltage regulation in the POI by injecting reactive power (Figure 44). During this voltage regulation, suddenly a frequency events appears, so the virtual inertia control reacts by providing power at the first event and absorbing power at the second event (Figure 45). It should be clarified that for frequency events a signal generator has been used in order to evaluate the control and HESS real response, so this control is only analysed in open loop.

NOTE: Due to the strength of the Iberian power grid, it is almost impossible to see a real frequency event, so signal generators have been used to deceive the measurement system into measuring a generated (fake) frequency.

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 44. Example 2: multiservice. Voltage regulation and virtual inertia (open loop).

Figure 45. Example 2: multiservice. Voltage regulation and virtual inertia (open loop).

3.4.2 Test Scenario2: HESS with PV Power Plant

To consider market parameters, another scenario is considered for multi service assessment. In this part of the paper the following figure shows the real operation of a 4.5 MWh and 2 MW BESS system together with a PV solar plant of 4 MW nominal power, both connected to a bus with access power of 2 MW. Figure 46 shows the basic representation of this second use case. The rest of the system data are presented in Table 10.

Figure 46. Second use case diagram.

Table 10. System Data considered.

Elements	Data
Maximum power of POI	2 MVA
Main grid transformer	7.1 MVA, 12/66 kV
BESS	2 MW, 4.5 MWh
BESS power converter	2.4 MVA
BESS transformer	2.5 MVA, 69/12 kV
PV Plant	4 MW, 4.2 MWp
PV power converter	4.1 MVA
PV transformer	4.2 MVA, 69/12 kV

The following figure shows the optimal operation for the use case described above. At the top it can be observed the SOC of the BESS in kWh in black, the production of the renewable resource in green, the power in the POI in red and the BESS charge power in yellow (when said curve is negative) and the discharge power of this (when said curve is positive). At the

bottom of the figure, the hourly prices of the day ahead energy market for said analysis days are represented in black.

In this multi-service example, it is observed how the BESS system does time shifting (shifting power injection into the grid to more expensive hours to maximize income) while storing the surplus renewable resource (renewable Resource Integration) due to the PV power produced is higher than the access power of 2 MW as the restriction of injected power at the POI (Figure 47).

In this multiservice example, this optimal operation was computed in the Grid core layer (located in the cloud, as it was described in the Figure 39), due to this use case is a market orientated operation. Then, in the physical layer (InMS® uGrid) it was computed the real charge and discharge BESS power, once there is a renewable resource (PV generation) and it has to be computed in real time the BESS power reference.

Figure 47. Multiservice: clipping and time shifting (day ahead market).

3.5 Benefits of the Multiservice Methodology for InterSTORE

Multi-service strategy holds significant importance, particularly in the context of HESS, for several key reasons:

- **Optimized Resource Utilization:** Multi-service strategy allows for the simultaneous provision of multiple services from a single ESS. In the context of hybrid energy storage, this means leveraging the same infrastructure to perform various functions such as peak shaving, frequency regulation, energy arbitrage, and backup power supply. By maximizing the utilization of resources, organizations can achieve higher efficiency and cost-effectiveness.
- **Enhanced Grid Stability and Resilience:** HESS equipped with multi-service capabilities can contribute to grid stability and resilience by providing ancillary services such as frequency regulation and voltage support, energy arbitrage. These services help to balance supply and demand fluctuations, mitigate grid disturbances, and enhance

overall system reliability, especially in the face of intermittent renewable energy sources.

- *Economic Viability:* By diversifying revenue streams through multi-service provision, HESS become economically more viable. Beyond simply storing and discharging energy, these systems can participate in various energy markets, earning revenue from services such as capacity markets, frequency regulation markets, and demand response programs. This diversification of income sources strengthens the business case for investment in energy storage infrastructure.
- *Flexibility and Adaptability:* Multi-service capability enhances the flexibility and adaptability of HESS to meet evolving energy needs and market conditions. As energy markets evolve and regulatory requirements change, these systems can quickly adjust their operational modes to capitalize on emerging opportunities or address new challenges. This agility is crucial for ensuring the long-term relevance and competitiveness of energy storage investments. From the results of the last case in section 3.4.2, it has been observed that how the optimization algorithm, situated in the Grid core control layer within the cloud, is highly effective in maximizing the economic returns of the entire power plant (comprising PV + BESS) through participation in the day-ahead energy market. Additionally, it has been noted how the physical control layer, located in the EMS, called InMS uGrid, efficiently utilizes all surplus solar resources by prioritizing the cheapest hours, thereby achieving maximum economic performance, particularly during central daylight hours.
- *Maximized Environmental Benefits:* HESS with multi-service capabilities can maximize their environmental benefits by enabling greater integration of renewable energy sources and facilitating the transition to a low-carbon energy system. By providing grid services such as frequency regulation and voltage support, these systems enable greater penetration of renewable energy while maintaining grid stability, thus accelerating the decarbonization of the energy sector.

In summary, multi-service strategy is crucial in the context of HESS as it enables optimized resource utilization, enhances grid stability and resilience, improves economic viability, enhances flexibility and adaptability, and maximizes environmental benefits. By leveraging the diverse capabilities of energy storage assets, organizations can unlock greater value and contribute to a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

4 Conclusions

The task concludes successfully, with the development of a practical HESS sizing tool with an integrated pipeline and presents the developments and verification results from such a proposed model. The model's modular design, divided in three phases, in which each phase operates independently, enhances flexibility, allowing for easy adjustments and updates to specific parts without impacting the entire model. This approach not only simplifies error isolation and troubleshooting, but also promotes scalability and reusability of components in different contexts. The validation of the model was based on a full optimization approach for assets sizing applied to renewable energy communities. The results are in line with the validation model, despite the latter not providing a range of viable options.

All requirements for the model development were fulfilled. Verifying the model, using real data clarified the procedure. We observe that even though viable solutions can mathematically be identified from the model output, they may not exist as a commercial solution. This strengthens the requirement to have an optimal area of solutions instead of a single option.

The hybrid storage sizing model shows the superiority of the hybrid system in terms of versatility, size and adaptability to physical constraints such when there is a need for:

- i) Storage capacity increase.
- ii) The case where one cannot rely on a single battery.
- iii) The case in which a given technology cannot be deployed in the same location as an already existing battery due to physical, security or other constraints.
- iv) Complementarity of characteristic and performances.

The model is provided opensource via GitHub [55], with the intention of assisting the readers and encouraging them to employ or further develop the model for their own projects or research endeavours.

Regarding the impact of integrating control strategies, the report focused on the coordination solution that integrates multi-service functionality within the system, focusing on a case study involving the effects of wind profiles and PV scenarios. According to the first case, the obtained results indicate that using only Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) leads to over-degradation of the battery due to its exposure to high-frequency wind variations. However, in a Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS), a smoothed power profile is achieved by utilizing Ultra-Capacitors (UCAP) with high-power technology to cover the high-frequency variations in wind. Consequently, the power battery is shielded from these rapid power fluctuations, preserving its degradation. It is important to note that due to size limitations of the UCAP, saturation of the State of Charge (SOC) is observed. A larger UCAP in the system would result in better responses, thereby mitigating SOC saturation issues.

In the case of setpoint following mode of operation, it has been observed that significant energy or capacity may be required in two situations:

- Firstly, when the setpoint significantly deviates from the actual wind production, necessitating sufficient capacity or energy from BESS/HESS to bridge the gap between the wind generation and the setpoint.
- Secondly, when the setpoint changes, there is a heightened demand for capacity or energy to ensure smooth ramp control.

Furthermore, it should be noted that this service is activated upon demand from Transmission System Operators (TSO) or power plant operators due to reliability or operational requirements. Additionally, for the successful implementation of this service, accurate forecasting is essential to meet all setpoints.

According to the obtained results from the last scenario (section 3.4.2) of multiservice test with PV plant and market factors, it has been observed that how the optimization algorithm, situated in the Grid core control layer within the cloud, is highly effective in maximizing the economic returns of the entire power plant (comprising PV + BESS) through participation in the day-ahead energy market. Additionally, it has been noted how the physical control layer, located in our EMS layer called InMS uGrid, efficiently utilizes all surplus solar resources by prioritizing the cheapest hours, thereby achieving maximum economic performance, particularly during central daylight hours, around 12:00.

Furthermore, it's noteworthy how the degradation model comes into play in this scenario: on the second example day (July 22), as illustrated in the [Figure 47](#), the BESS isn't fully charged; it only receives excess solar energy. This is because the cost associated with cycling the batteries outweighs the profit margin from price differences on that day. Hence, it's deemed suboptimal to subject the batteries to increased degradation through cycling, considering the benefit derived from charging and discharging the batteries with 100% energy sourced from the external grid. This degradation model ensures the optimization of the storage system's useful lifespan against potential income that fails to offset degradation losses.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] R. Hemmati, H. Saboori, Emergence of hybrid energy storage systems in renewable energy and transport applications – A review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 65 (2016) 11–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.06.029>.
- [2] F. Nadeem, S.M.S. Hussain, P.K. Tiwari, A.K. Goswami, T.S. Ustun, Comparative Review of Energy Storage Systems, Their Roles, and Impacts on Future Power Systems, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 4555–4585. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2888497>.
- [3] A.A. Kebede, T. Kalogiannis, J. Van Mierlo, M. Berecibar, A comprehensive review of stationary energy storage devices for large scale renewable energy sources grid integration, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 159 (2022) 112213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112213>.
- [4] A.S. Jacob, R. Banerjee, P.C. Ghosh, Sizing of hybrid energy storage system for a PV based microgrid through design space approach, *Appl Energy* 212 (2018) 640–653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.12.040>.
- [5] D. Niu, J. Fang, W. Yau, S.M. Goetz, Comprehensive evaluation of energy storage systems for inertia emulation and frequency regulation improvement, *Energy Reports* 9 (2023) 2566–2576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.01.110>.
- [6] S. Günther, A. Bensmann, R. Hanke-Rauschenbach, Theoretical dimensioning and sizing limits of hybrid energy storage systems, *Appl Energy* 210 (2018) 127–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.10.116>.
- [7] E.W. Schaefer, G. Hoogsteen, J.L. Hurink, R.P. van Leeuwen, Sizing of hybrid energy storage through analysis of load profile characteristics: A household case study, *J Energy Storage* 52 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.104768>.
- [8] S. Hajiaghahi, A. Salemnia, M. Hamzeh, Hybrid energy storage system for microgrids applications: A review, *J Energy Storage* 21 (2019) 543–570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2018.12.017>.
- [9] S. Günther, L. Weber, A.L. Bensmann, R. Hanke-Rauschenbach, Structured Analysis and Review of Filter-Based Control Strategies for Hybrid Energy Storage Systems, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 126269–126284. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3226261>.
- [10] N. Korada, M.K. Mishra, Grid Adaptive Power Management Strategy for an Integrated Microgrid With Hybrid Energy Storage, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 64 (2017) 2884–2892. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2016.2631443>.
- [11] L.W. Chong, Y.W. Wong, R.K. Rajkumar, R.K. Rajkumar, D. Isa, Hybrid energy storage systems and control strategies for stand-alone renewable energy power systems, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 66 (2016) 174–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.07.059>.
- [12] X. Lin, R. Zamora, Controls of hybrid energy storage systems in microgrids: Critical review, case study and future trends, *J Energy Storage* 47 (2022) 103884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2021.103884>.
- [13] Y. Yang, S. Bremner, C. Menictas, M. Kay, Battery energy storage system size determination in renewable energy systems: A review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 91 (2018) 109–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.03.047>.

- [14] B. Xiong, Y. Yang, J. Tang, Y. Li, Z. Wei, Y. Su, Q. Zhang, An Enhanced Equivalent Circuit Model of Vanadium Redox Flow Battery Energy Storage Systems Considering Thermal Effects, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 162297–162308. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2952212>.
- [15] T.S. Babu, K.R. Vasudevan, V.K. Ramachandaramurthy, S.B. Sani, S. Chemud, R.M. Lajim, A Comprehensive Review of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems: Converter Topologies, Control Strategies and Future Prospects, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 148702–148721. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3015919>.
- [16] M.H. Ali, D. Slaifstein, F.M. Ibanez, C. Zugschwert, M. Pugach, Power Management Strategies for Vanadium Redox Flow Battery and Supercapacitors in Hybrid Energy Storage Systems, in: *IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe*, IEEE Computer Society, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGT-Europe54678.2022.9960352>.
- [17] W.E. Org, K. Gokce, A. Ozdemir, A Rule Based Power Split Strategy for Battery/Ultracapacitor Energy Storage Systems in Hybrid Electric Vehicles, 2016. www.electrochemsci.org.
- [18] Y. Ye, H. Wang, B. Xu, J. Zhang, An imitation learning-based energy management strategy for electric vehicles considering battery aging, *Energy* 283 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.128537>.
- [19] A. Aktaş, Y. Kırçiçek, A novel optimal energy management strategy for offshore wind/marine current/battery/ultracapacitor hybrid renewable energy system, *Energy* 199 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.117425>.
- [20] S.A. Ghorashi Khalil Abadi, S.I. Habibi, T. Khalili, A. Bidram, A Model Predictive Control Strategy for Performance Improvement of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in DC Microgrids, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 25400–25421. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3155668>.
- [21] Y.R. Challapuram, G.M. Quintero, S.B. Bayne, A.S. Subburaj, M.A. Harral, Electrical Equivalent Model of Vanadium Redox Flow Battery, in: *2019 IEEE Green Technologies Conference (GreenTech)*, 2019: pp. 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/GreenTech.2019.8767145>.
- [22] C. Zugschwert, S. Goschl, F. Martin Ibanez, K.H. Pettinger, Development of a multi-Timescale method for classifying hybrid energy storage systems in grid applications, in: *2021 6th IEEE Workshop on the Electronic Grid, EGRID 2021*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/eGRID52793.2021.9662136>.
- [23] Y. Wang, W. Li, Z. Liu, L. Li, An Energy Management Strategy for Hybrid Energy Storage System Based on Reinforcement Learning, *World Electric Vehicle Journal* 14 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj14030057>.
- [24] F. Li, Y. Gao, Y. Wu, Y. Xia, C. Wang, J. Hu, Z. Huang, Incentive learning-based energy management for hybrid energy storage system in electric vehicles, *Energy Convers Manag* 293 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117480>.
- [25] J. Duan, Z. Yi, D. Shi, C. Lin, X. Lu, Z. Wang, Reinforcement-Learning-Based Optimal Control of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in Hybrid AC–DC Microgrids, *IEEE Trans Industr Inform* 15 (2019) 5355–5364. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tii.2019.2896618>.
- [26] P. Ranjbaran, J. Ebrahimi, A. Bakhshai, P. Jain, Reinforcement Learning-Based Approaches to Energy Management of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in Electric

- Vehicles, in: Proceedings of the International Conference on Power Electronics and Drive Systems, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PEDS57185.2023.10246568>.
- [27] R. Xiong, J. Cao, Q. Yu, Reinforcement learning-based real-time power management for hybrid energy storage system in the plug-in hybrid electric vehicle, *Appl Energy* 211 (2018) 538–548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.11.072>.
- [28] D. Kang, D. Kang, S. Hwangbo, H. Niaz, W.B. Lee, J.J. Liu, J. Na, Optimal planning of hybrid energy storage systems using curtailed renewable energy through deep reinforcement learning, *Energy* 284 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.128623>.
- [29] M. Möller, D. Kucevic, N. Collath, A. Parlikar, P. Dotzauer, B. Tepe, S. Englberger, A. Jossen, H. Hesse, SimSES: A holistic simulation framework for modeling and analyzing stationary energy storage systems, *J Energy Storage* 49 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2021.103743>.
- [30] C. Schubert, W.F. Hassen, B. Poisl, S. Seitz, J. Schubert, E. Oyarbide Usabiaga, P.M. Gaudo, K.H. Pettinger, Hybrid Energy Storage Systems Based on Redox-Flow Batteries: Recent Developments, Challenges, and Future Perspectives, *Batteries* 9 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries9040211>.
- [31] S. Cheng, W.-B. Sun, W.-L. Liu, Multi-Objective Configuration Optimization of a Hybrid Energy Storage System, *Applied Sciences* 7 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app7020163>.
- [32] European Commission, European Commission, (2024). https://commission.europa.eu/index_en (accessed April 24, 2024).
- [33] Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, Long-term Strategy for a Modern, Competitive and Climate Neutral Spanish Economy in 2050, (2020).
- [34] Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan, (2021).
- [35] Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, The international process to combat climate change - The European Union, (n.d.). <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/el-proceso-internacional-de-lucha-contra-el-cambio-climatico/la-union-europea.html> (accessed April 24, 2024).
- [36] European Commission, 2040 Climate Target, (2024). https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/2040-climate-target_en (accessed April 24, 2024).
- [37] REE, Estudios de prospectiva del sistema y necesidades para su operabilidad, (2020).
- [38] ENTSO-E, System dynamic and operational challenges, (2023). <https://tyndp.entsoe.eu/resources/system-dynamic-and-operational-challenges> (accessed April 24, 2024).
- [39] F. Iglesias, W. Kastner, Analysis of Similarity Measures in Times Series Clustering for the Discovery of Building Energy Patterns, *Energies* 2013, Vol. 6, Pages 579–597 6 (2013) 579–597. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN6020579>.
- [40] N. Sarajpoor, L. Rakai, J. Arteaga, H. Zareipour, A Shape-Based Clustering Framework for Time Aggregation in the Presence of Variable Generation and Energy Storage, *IEEE*

- Open Access Journal of Power and Energy 8 (2021) 448–459. <https://doi.org/10.1109/OAJPE.2021.3097366>.
- [41] T. Warren Liao, Clustering of time series data—a survey, *Pattern Recognit* 38 (2005) 1857–1874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2005.01.025>.
- [42] P. Senin, Dynamic Time Warping Algorithm Review, *Information and Computer Science Department University of Hawaii at Manoa Honolulu* 40 (2008) 1–23.
- [43] R. van der Vlist, C. Taal, R. Heusdens, Tracking Recurring Patterns in Time Series Using Dynamic Time Warping, in: *2019 27th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, 2019: pp. 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.23919/EUSIPCO.2019.8903102>.
- [44] W.W. Tso, C.D. Demirhan, C.F. Heuberger, J.B. Powell, E.N. Pistikopoulos, A hierarchical clustering decomposition algorithm for optimizing renewable power systems with storage, *Appl Energy* 270 (2020) 115190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115190>.
- [45] E.C. Bobric, G. Cartina, G. Grigoraş, Clustering techniques in load profile analysis for distribution stations, *Advances in Electrical and Computer Engineering* 9 (2009) 63–66. <https://doi.org/10.4316/AECE.2009.01011>.
- [46] S. Pineda, J.M. Morales, Chronological Time-Period Clustering for Optimal Capacity Expansion Planning With Storage, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 33 (2018) 7162–7170. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2842093>.
- [47] I. Prahastono, D. King, C.S. Ozveren, A review of Electricity Load Profile Classification methods, in: *2007 42nd International Universities Power Engineering Conference*, 2007: pp. 1187–1191. <https://doi.org/10.1109/UPEC.2007.4469120>.
- [48] R. Ma, *Clustering of Time Series Data: Measures, Methods, and Applications*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.57709/20253148>.
- [49] Vijaya, S. Sharma, N. Batra, Comparative Study of Single Linkage, Complete Linkage, and Ward Method of Agglomerative Clustering, in: *2019 International Conference on Machine Learning, Big Data, Cloud and Parallel Computing (COMITCon)*, 2019: pp. 568–573. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMITCon.2019.8862232>.
- [50] K. Potter, J. Kniss, R. Riesenfeld, C.R. Johnson, Visualizing summary statistics and uncertainty, *Computer Graphics Forum* 29 (2010) 823–832. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8659.2009.01677.x>.
- [51] Torqeedo, Datasheet - Deep Blue Battery 80, Torqeedo Co. (2023). <https://media.torqeedo.com/downloads/technical-data/torqeedo-deep-blue-battery-80-technical-data-sheet-v1.2.pdf> (accessed March 26, 2024).
- [52] Dawnice Co., 200 kW Lithium Battery, Dawnice (2024). <https://www.energydawnice.com/dawnice-100-kw-200-kwh-300-kwh-400-kwh-500-kw-battery-storage/> (accessed March 26, 2024).
- [53] Generac Industrial Power, 250kW-battery-data-sheet-new-logo, Generac Industrial Power Co. (2024). <https://www.generac.com/Industrial/GeneracIndustrialPower/media/library/Downloads/A0003997951-SBE-500-LFP-final.pdf> (accessed March 26, 2024).
- [54] R. Rocha, R. Silva, J. Mello, S. Faria, F. Retorta, C. Gouveia, J. Villar, A Three-Stage Model to Manage Energy Communities, Share Benefits and Provide Local Grid Services, *Energies (Basel)* 16 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16031143>.

- [55] A. Lucas, S. Golmaryami, S. Carvalhosa, GitHub - Hybrid Storage Sizing Methodology, GitHub (2024). <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Hybrid-Storage-Sizing-Model> (accessed January 15, 2024).

6 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Technology characteristics, based on [1-3].....	11
Table 2. Describes variables and constraints.....	34
Table 3. Describes variables and constraints.....	36
Table 4. Optimal solution of dispatch.	38
Table 5. Optimal solution of dispatch.	41
Table 6. Example of two proposed BES systems.	45
Table 7. Example of commercial technology in the market.	48
Table 8. Technical parameters of studied benchmark (I).....	62
Table 9. Technical parameters from HESS system (II).....	63
Table 10. System Data considered.....	67

7 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Technology classification according to discharge times.....	10
Figure 2. Concept of control strategy for HESS [11].	12
Figure 3. Diagram of the control structure for HESS: (a) Centralized, (b) Distributed, (c) Decentralized adopted by [12].	13
Figure 4. Benefits of HESS [15].	14
Figure 5. Classification of HESS control techniques [15].	15
Figure 6. Sizing techniques of BESS data collected from [13].	15
Figure 7. Flowchart of probabilistic methods collected from [13].	16
Figure 8. Flowchart of analytical methods collected from [13].	16
Figure 9. Flowchart of direct search-based methods collected from [13].	17
Figure 10. The general framework of an RL-based EMS of HESS was adopted by [26].	20
Figure 11. Summary of different aspects of RL-based EMS in HESS by [26].	21
Figure 12. Shows the architecture of the energy management system in real-time [30].	22
Figure 13. Greenhouse gas emissions 2015-250. Source: European Commission [36].	25
Figure 14. LTS main goals. Source: ELP.	26
Figure 15. Long-term Decarbonisation Strategy. Source: ELP.	26
Figure 16. Hybridization model approach.	28
Figure 17. Recurring pattern identification approach.	29
Figure 18. Differences between Euclidean and DTW algorithms from two daily load profiles.	31
Figure 19. Dendrogram of 363 data points.	31
Figure 20. Identify the most representative recurring pattern.	32
Figure 21. (a) Box plot of 210 data points in a recurring pattern; (b) determine the median of the load profile.	33
Figure 22. Recurring load as input.	39
Figure 23. Optimal dispatch of the battery.	39
Figure 24. Battery SOE at the beginning of each hour during the cycle.	40
Figure 25. Elbow method for battery capacity identification.	40
Figure 26. A detailed flowchart of the hybridization model is shown in step 3.	42
Figure 27. (a) Signal cut-off example of 50%; (b) and Hybridization curve example.	44
Figure 28. Hybridization curve.	45
Figure 29. Hybridization curve.	47
Figure 30. Ragone plot illustrates technology selection by power and energy capacity range, derived from data in Table 1.	48
Figure 31. Ragone plot illustrates technology selection by power and energy capacity range, derived from data in Table 7.	49
Figure 32. Wind+PV vs total generation (ENTSO-E, 2023) [38].	53
Figure 33. Inertia constant (ENTSO-E, 2023) [38].	54
Figure 34. Frequency (Hz) in steady-state vs time (%) (REE, 2020) [37].	54
Figure 35. Imbalance leading to 1 Hz/s RoCoF (ENTSO-E, 2023) [38].	55
Figure 36. Iberian Peninsula vs Europe max. RoCoF (Hz/s) vs time (%) (REE, 2020) [37].	55
Figure 37. Grid services represented over the frame of a Ragone Plot.	58
Figure 38. Hybrid concept, avoiding oversizing depicted over a Ragone diagram.	59
Figure 39. HESStec multiservice basic diagram.	61
Figure 40. Use case for multiservice example 1.	62
Figure 41. Example 1: multiservice test, POI measured signal assessment.	64
Figure 42. Example 1: multiservice test, POI signal: Power battery assessment.	64
Figure 43. Example 1: multiservice test, UCAP assessment.	65

D3.1 – HESS Dimensioning Methodology for Efficient Integration Report

Figure 44. Example 2: multiservice. Voltage regulation and virtual inertia (open loop).....	66
Figure 45. Example 2: multiservice. Voltage regulation and virtual inertia (open loop).....	66
Figure 46. Second use case diagram.	67
Figure 47. Multiservice: clipping and time shifting (day ahead market).	68

